

The Finnish Inventory Programme for the Underwater Marine Environment (Velmu)

Methodology guide 2025

Version 24.3.2025

The methodology guide is provided as a compressed file. i.e.
Velmu_method method instructions_2025.zip

The methodology guide includes the following appendices as separate files:

- LajiGIS - tallennusohje 6 - videot (meri).pdf*
- LajiGIS - tallennusohje 7 - sukellukset (meri).pdf*
- Excelin esitarkastus LajiGISiä varten.docx*
- LajiGIS - Uhanalaisseurantakohteen tallentaminen.docx*
- Excel marine data spreadsheet_dropvideo.xlsm*
- Excel marine data spreadsheet_point survey.xlsm*
- Excel marine data spreadsheet_diveline.xlsm*
- Instructions for maritime forms.pdf*
- Benthic sampling field protocol version 20180525.doc*
- Field protocol filling instructions version 20180525.doc*
- POHJE-definition protocol.doc*
- Velmu Field protocols_01062018.xlsx (+ .pdf)*
 (includes diving and video protocols, field diary, diving report, and method codes)

Method guide update log

Date	Event/change	Acknowledgement
1.6.2018	2018 general update ready	Ari Laine
5.6.2018	Presented and accepted by the Velmu project group	Ari Laine
8.6.2018	Added a dive evaluation substrate-specific assessment option to the manual (Chapter 7, paragraph 5d)	Ari Laine
28.2.2019	Finnish version translated to English	Kevin O'Brien
12.6.2019	Check of contents and minor additions	Ari Laine
22.4.2019	Red list 2019 changes and other threatened species related changes made, wading added as a method	Essi Keskinen
12.6.2019	1) Inventory planning, simplified: A more detailed field plan than the spatial plan specifies <i>the mapping areas and methods to be used</i> 2) Added use of a footer to name videos: Duplicates such as GoPro videos from the same video point must be named with the same video name, but with a separate subtitle (e.g.a, b, c) and this name shall be entered on the field protocol and on the LajiGIS field form under "video ID". 3) More specified mapping point naming conventions: <i>For field sampling, only a serial number can be entered into the positioning equipment as a point identifier, but when storing the data, care must be taken to re-associate this identifier with the area-year-boat identifier.</i> 4) Table 1, corrected Randomised -> Split random sampling 5) Alien species, added Murchisonellidae 6) Method for identification of benthic animals from diving and video, modified <i>Galerucella nymphaea</i> to number of individuals and <i>Laomedea loveni</i> to cover, added <i>Cordylophora caspia</i> , cover	Ari Laine

	<p>7) Added Chapter 7 Item 4: The diver estimates the amount of vegetation and animals</p> <p>8) Added Chapter 7 Item 5d: <i>Note. species occurring as epiphytic are marked and stored in the SpeciesGIS system with their own identifier.</i></p> <p>9) Added Chapter 7, point 5e: can also be assessed as prevalence</p>	
13.6.2019	Updated Chapter 6 "Priority species" to meet Finnish species threat assessments 2019	Essi Keskinen
27.2.2020	Updated Chapter 6 remaining species to correspond to endangered species assessments for Finnish species 2019, entries in the Hertta Species database removed, and data collected on endangered species updated, wading added	Essi Keskinen
11.1.2021	Added to Chapter 6 guidance on recording fish spawn findings	Ari Laine
15.1.2021	Updated In Chapter 3, the naming policy for videos and mapping points	Ari Laine
21.1.2021	Updated attachments: updated SpeciesGIS recording instructions, replaced old sea form with three separate forms and related instructions.	Ari Laine
22.1.2021	Added Chapter 3: Recording guide for single species	Ari Laine
12.11.2021	Added paragraph Taxonomic linking to Chapter 6. Added paragraph defining species occurring at the extremes of their distribution and depth occurrence. Added <i>Rangia cuneata</i> and <i>Sinelobus vanhareeni</i> to the alien species. References has been added to the species literature.	Ari Laine
26.11.2021	New text added to Finnish version translated and inserted parts rearranged to match the most up to date Finnish version	Kevin O'Brien
14.2.2022	Additional changes made to comply with the latest Finnish version (14.2.2022)	Ari Laine
18.3.2025	VELMU has changed its spelling to Velmu. The section titles related to diving mapping (7) have been changed to transect and single-point mapping (8), sections 7-10 have been rearranged, and subheadings added (including point mapping). In addition, the term "dive line" has been changed to "vegetation line" or "transect" in the text (since these cover all depth lines and methods), while "diver" is now "biological surveyor".	Essi Keskinen
24.3.2025	Benthic sampling tube operated by diver – diameter changed from 4,5 cm to 8 cm	Ari Laine
7.4.2026	Recording fish observations has been changed from recommended to mandatory when conducting field surveys.	Essi Keskinen

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Abbreviations and glossary

Aquascope – A viewing tool used as a mask substitute to help with diving lines while wading or from a boat, which allows you to see under the surface.

ArcGIS – Spatial information software with tools for the analysis and modelling of spatial data, forecasting and risk analysis, as well as custom map markings and legends.

Benthic fauna sampling protocol - A form to be filled in at sea, from which the recorded information, along with species observations, is exported to the POHJE system.

Dive line – This mapping method is suitable for accurate species mapping and can be carried out by diving, snorkelling or wading.

Drop-video – A video system that is lowered to the seafloor and used to describe the underwater habitat at a given sampling point.

EUNIS – A classification system for habitats produced by the European Environment Agency.

Global Positioning System (GPS) – Satellite positioning system developed by the US Department of Defense, officially called Navstar GPS. This system offers the possibility of accurate, real-time and one-way positioning.

HELCOM – Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission - Helsinki Commission.

HERTTA-system – An information system developed and maintained by the environmental administration, including data sets on water resources, waterworks, surface water status, groundwater, species, environmental loads, use of areas, map service and code lists.

Kautsky square – Sampler used by SCUBA diver to collect hard bottom invertebrate animals. Usually consists of a 20 cm x 20 cm metal frame attached to a fine-meshed net bag.

LajiGIS – Spatial data application maintained by Metsähallitus, used for the management and maintenance of species-related information, as well as for the planning and monitoring of species in the field.

LajiGIS-Excel marine protocol – A Microsoft® Excel file where Velmu mapping information is stored prior to its transfer to the LajiGIS system (Except bottom animal surveys, which are recorded on the benthic fauna field-sampling protocol).

Petite Ponar – A small grab that can be operated without a winch to sample soft bottom invertebrates.

POHJE-system – Part of the HERTTA environmental information system, which records spatial information observations of monitoring, Velmu and other benthic faunal surveys.

Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) – Remote-controlled robot video camera capable of photographing or videoing the seabed structure and biota from the surface.

Ultra Short baseline (USBL) – An underwater positioning system used to locate ROV movements under the surface.

Van Veen grab – This is a traditional grab sampler for collecting invertebrate bottom fauna from soft sediments.

Velmu – The Underwater Marine Nature Inventory Programme (2004-2015), which charted the diversity of the underwater marine environment in Finnish coastal areas.

World Geodetic System 84 (WGS84) – A coordinate system and associated geoid model defined and maintained by the US Department of Defense. The GPS system and the latest marine charts are based on the WGS84 coordinate system.

Preface

During the first phase (2004-2015) of the Underwater Marine Biodiversity Inventory Programme, also known as the Velmu programme, an overview was obtained of the distribution of species and habitats in Finnish marine areas, as well as information on bottom quality and the occurrence of geological formations. In particular, Velmu1 surveyed the geological structure of the seabed, the physical and hydrographic characteristics of the water column, and the distribution of biological habitats and fish breeding areas along the entire Finnish coastline. Velmu's second phase, i.e. Velmu2, will continue the work of mapping underwater marine nature in the field, with particular focus on poorly known species, habitats and habitats.

The aim of the surveys is to find areas of unique natural value and to investigate the distribution and ecological status of rare and endangered underwater habitats and species. Survey results are transferred to databases where they can be used to build prediction models for the distribution of species and underwater habitats. The maps produced are published as part of the map and information service developed by the Velmu programme.

The data and prediction models produced by Velmu are utilised in the implementation of both national and international obligations related to underwater diversity in the Baltic Sea (Water Framework Directive, Habitats Directive, Marine Strategy Directive, HELCOM Baltic Sea Protection Action Program, Biodiversity Agreement), as well as background information, e.g. in marine spatial planning. Velmu's information needs and related policy processes are presented in a document (in Finnish) by the Ministry of the Environment entitled "Policy processes for protecting marine biodiversity - what Velmu information is needed and at what stage the information is input into different processes" (<https://www.ymparisto.fi/download/noname/%7BA10F82D7-258D-4DD2-8810-5F9B0DDDED35%7D/132233>).

The Velmu programme is managed by the Ministry of the Environment together with a steering group, while the Finnish Environment Institute's Maritime Centre is responsible for coordinating it. The operational activities of Velmu are managed by the coordinator Mr. Markku Viitasalo from the Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE) together with the project team.

In addition to SYKE, the Velmu programme also incorporates coastal ELY centres (Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment), Metsähallitus, the Geological Survey of Finland, the Natural Resources Centre (LUKE), Åbo Akademi University and the Naval Academy Maritime Research Centre. In addition, consultants, including other authorities and non-governmental organisations also participate occasionally. Due to the large number of participants, a unified methodological guide is needed to make the results comparable. The purpose of this manual is to unify and document the methods used in Velmu to create a framework for producing reliable and comparable information. In updating this guideline, particular attention has been paid to ensuring that the creation and storage of new data is also compatible with new information systems. All project surveys conducted within Velmu are planned and implemented in accordance with this guide. However, it should be noted that this manual is generic and may not be suitable for the entire coastline. Data collection methods must therefore be adapted to the specific characteristics of sea areas, such that the overall comparison is not compromised. Therefore, if one decides to

deviate from the methods outlined in this guide, it is advisable to agree in advance with the coordinating body.

Together, the Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE) and Metsähallitus Parks & Wildlife Finland (MH) have been the most recent editors of the method guidelines, with regular updates over the years. Other contributions have also been made by the various ELY centres (Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment). Writers have included Anna Arnkil (MH), Heidi Arponen (MH), Eva Ehrnsten (Southeast Finland ELY-centre), Jaakko Haapamäki (Southwest Finland ELY-centre), Ville Karvinen (SYKE), Essi Keskinen (MH), Suvi Kiviluoto (Southwest Finland ELY-centre), Mira Korpi (MH), Kirsi Kostamo (SYKE), Lasse Kurvinen (MH), Katriina Könönen (MH), Rami Laaksonen (Southwest Finland ELY-centre), Ari Laine (MH), Maiju Lanki (MH), Juho Lappalainen (SYKE), Pekka Lehtonen (MH), Aija Nieminen (MH), Kevin O'Brien (MH), Anu Riihimäki (MH), Heta Rousi (SYKE), Elina Salo (South Ostrobothnia ELY-centre), Mats Westerbom (MH).

1. Inventory planning

In Velmu, the target areas for mapping are planned prior to the field season. based on the inventory strategy and information needs, and the proposal for the areas of activity is approved by the steering group. The plan for the area of activity is defined by both targeted and randomised mapping areas, as well as the methods to be applied in relation to the resources available. If necessary, the plan also prioritises which areas to map and which to defer to subsequent years.

For example, the locations of dive lines and points are shown in field plans mainly as area boundaries, as field conditions largely determine where mapping work can be done safely. Moreover, due to wind conditions, settlement or popular boat routes (not limited to official fairways), it is only possible to determine the final mapping location in the field. However, it is advisable to check both sea charts and aerial imagery in advance for suitable locations. Randomisation is often important for the use of such data, which is why mapping points are randomised in advance whenever possible.

Suitability	Dive line	Dive point	Drop-video	ROV mapping	Hard bottom benthic samples	Soft bottom benthic samples (includes sand)	Plant community invertebrate samples (Fucus-bag)	Sidescan sonar	Aquascope	Rake (thrown/handle)	Drone imagery
Depth zone (m)	0-20 (-30)	0-5	2-60	5-60	Currently 0-6, theoretically 0-30	>1	0-6	2-60	0-2	0-3	0-2
Species											
Shoreline /Aerial shoot vascular plants	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	1	2
Submerged leaf vascular plants	3	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	2	2
Mobile/Floating/ floating leaf vascular plants	3	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	1	2
Macrophytic algae	3	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	3	1	1
Charophytes	3	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	3	2	2
Aquatic mosses	3	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	3	2	1
Sessile macroscopic benthic fauna	3	3	1	1	3	0	0	0	2	0	0
Hard bottom benthic fauna	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infaunal benthic fauna	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0
Macrophyte-dwelling benthic fauna	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
Fish	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nature types	3	3	3	3	1	1	1	3	3	1	3
Key habitats	3	3	3	3	1	1	1	3	3	1	3
Poorly known species and habitats	3	3	1	1	2	2	2	0	2	1	1
Threatened species and habitats	3	3	1	1	2	2	2	0	2	1	1
Invasive species	3	3	1	1	2	2	2	0	2	1	0
Rubbish	3	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Bottom topography	2	1	1	2	0	0	0	3	0	0	1
Bottom quality (different substrates)	3	3	3	3	0	2	0	2	3	0	1
Sedimentation amount	3	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Quantitativeness	2	2	2	2	3	3	1	1	2	0	1
Local coverage	3	1	1	2	2	1	2	3	2	3	3
Regional coverage	1	2	3	1	2	3	2	2	2	2	3
Cost effectiveness	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	3	2

Fig. 1. A suitability matrix of methods currently used in Velmu to collect different information. 3 = Well suited, 2 = partially suited, 1 = Poorly suited, 0 = Unsuitable.

2. Spatial information for surveys

The coordinate system

Sampling point coordinates are always stored in the **WGS84 coordinate system in the degrees and decimal degrees format (DD, dddd)**

N59.725166 E22.59516

However, the coordinates can be represented in many different ways. For example, in electronic navigation devices, they are often expressed in degrees, minutes, and minute decimals (DD ° MM.mmm) in the form N59°43.510 'E022°35.710'.

Nevertheless, the coordinates should always be converted into degrees and decimal degrees. If the GPS device used supports decimal degrees, it makes sense to set this as the default coordinate format. Otherwise, it is the responsibility of the surveyor to convert the coordinates to the standard Velmu WGS84 format shown above before the coordinates are transferred to the LajiGIS marine protocol.

The accuracy of all coordinates must be checked before entering data into any databases. This is done by projecting the coordinates onto a basemap and visually checking that the points are in the correct positions. Only a data collector who can verify where the data has been collected from in the field should do this. It should be noted that the location accuracy of conventional GPS devices can vary up to tens of metres. Thus, when saving coordinates in the field, you must be alert to the accuracy of your location. While collecting data, it is necessary to check that the position fix ability of the GPS device is functioning correctly and optimally with respect to the prevailing conditions.

Other mapping location information

The location name. The name of the location of the mapping point or dive line should be entered in the field protocol. Similarly, the name of the area is also recorded, including the necessary compass directions (e.g. Black Island N (region), Saddle (name of the islet)). The purpose is to establish a consistent naming convention based on a valid sea chart. If there is no name, surveyors should indicate the name of the nearest island and estimate the distance to the island and direction (e.g. anonymous Skerry, 1 km east of Saddle islet).

3. Saving data to information systems

The collected data will be stored in the existing Microsoft® Excel LajiGIS marine protocol. All protocols used during the field surveys will be archived, making it possible to return to them later. Entering information into information systems requires usernames to be applied for in a timely manner for those who will be recording the results. The data storage system is operated by the Metsähallitus LajiGIS application.

LajiGIS is part of the Uljas spatial dataset maintained by Metsähallitus and is used for the management and maintenance of species-related information, as well as for the planning and monitoring activities of species or biota. Although species observations from different surveys will be stored in the LajiGIS regardless of the threat status, monitoring sites for endangered species that match the data points of the HERTTA information system can also be stored there. Data storage to the LajiGIS system from the earlier years of Velmu's mapping data began in early 2018.

The HERTTA information system of the Finnish Environmental Administration consists of basic information systems serving the functions of environmental loading and control, water resources and environmental monitoring, including nature conservation and the planning, use and control of areas. HERTTA also variously uses spatial data sets in environmental management and is intended as a basic tool for those in need of environmental information. The key objective of the system has been to enhance the utilisation of environmental information packages. Use of the system is free of charge and training is available. The system is maintained and managed by the Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE).

Benthic fauna observations. The data collected by Velmu's benthic fauna sampling is stored in the POHJE information system. Field observations are recorded in the POHJE Field Data protocol (Appendix II). The results of the field surveys are compiled into the coastal monitoring site information protocol, from which they are transferred directly to the information system.

Endangered species. Observations of endangered species from Velmu-species surveys are compiled after the field season from the LajiGIS marine field protocols to the LajiGIS information system. For these observations monitoring objects (seurantakode) need to be made afterwards in LajiGIS (see attached guide).

NB! In 2019, the findings of endangered species have only been recorded on the LajiGIS marine protocols.

Single species surveys. When mapping the occurrence of only one species (e.g an alien- or a specific endangered species), the data is recorded in a LajiGIS basic form (not a marine form) from which it is aggregated into the LajiGIS application. Any possible bottom quality and depth data are recorded in the survey notes.

Species uncertainty and sample identification requirements

Species uncertainty is recorded if a particular species cannot be determined from the sample. Ambiguous samples should be preserved and submitted for identification to an expert for that species group. The uncertain observation is recorded in the LajiGIS Microsoft® Excel marine protocol in the "Requires checking" column with the code "Uncertain Determination/Detection (91)". If a sample is to be returned, enter the code "sample identification to be checked (31)" into the LajiGIS marine protocol. This label can also be used to keep a register of all samples that are still waiting to be identified. After a definite identification, the "Requires checking" field can be emptied.

Invasive species. Observations on alien species are recorded in the LajiGIS marine protocol and stored in the information system, similar to other spatial data. Findings of possible new, unusual or conspicuous species of invertebrates and fish are reported to Maiju Lehtiniemi (maiju.lehtiniemi@syke.fi) and Lauri Urho (lauri.urho@luke.fi), respectively. It should be noted that such data is still collected in all databases.

In addition to other species information, 'Description of location site' and 'Description of species observation' are recorded for invasive species. For example:

Description of the site: "South of Sandö Island, big stone on the beach."

Description: "On a stone with about 1 m² of vegetation growth."

Video and photo naming conventions

Videos are named as follows:

Videos recorded in the field are stored on external hard drives during the field season. It is recommended to back up these videos to a different location already at this time. The folder year, mapping destination and, if necessary, the date must be easily determined from the folder path. After analysis, the video files are exported from the external hard disks to RAID drives for storage.

An example of good folder hierarchy is as follows:

Municipality/Year/Region/Location name/ddmmyyyy/Original GoPro file
number_60N145416_25E091115_6.mpg

For example:

Vaasa/2020/Raippaluoto/Fäliskäret1/06062020/GOPR4143_60N145416_25E091115_6.mpg

The name of the video file is in the format GOPR4143_60N145416_25E091115_6.mpg, where the underscore separates the video ID, N and E coordinates, and the depth rounded to the nearest whole number.

When naming videos in the field, it's important to name individual videos so that they are clearly distinguishable from each other. When you use a GoPro camera, it automatically creates a unique ID for each video file. However, these are not displayed until the files are transferred to computer. The proven method has been to either record the ID written on paper at the beginning of the video or to say the unique ID (usually the waypoint of the GPS device) to the camera in a loud enough voice to make it easy to combine the video with field form data for analysis. If two different videos have been recorded from a video point (for example, using both DeepCam and GoPro video cameras), these videos should be compatible with each other afterwards. All videos shot at a single survey location, regardless of the device used, are stored in a folder with the same name as the survey site. The name of the survey site should be natural, e.g. the name of a nearby island as shown in a sea chart. When analysing videos, the video files must be renamed so that the video ID [column AV] generated by the Excel user form matches the name of the video file found on the computer. The user form in Excel generates this name automatically, and you can also use the form to name the video file.

Photographs are named as follows:

Region_placename-subject_dd-mm-
yyyy_ORGANISATION_Forename_Lastname_filename.jpeg

For example:

EGF_Black_lagoon_pike_Esox_lucius_13092016_METSAHALLITUS_Philip_Photographer_5104.jpeg

OBS! To ensure that the photographs and videos are named coherently, they are always named in Finnish, i.e., Finnish abbreviations and the names of organisations are always used. In addition, the latin names for species are also used.

Marine areas in the filenames are abbreviated as follows:

ISL= Eastern Gulf of Finland
LSL = Western Gulf of Finland
SAM = Archipelago Sea
SEM = Bothnian Sea
MEK = Kvarken
PEM = Gulf of Bothnia

Naming Survey points

In the field, each survey point is given a waypoint ID, which is obtained from a GPS device. In addition, the area to be mapped, i.e. the name of the survey location, must be marked on the field protocol. When you enter data in an Excel spreadsheet user form, the final name of the item automatically consists of the region name, year, and point ID. (For example, in 2020, a mapping point was taken with a GPS device near Isosaari island. Thus, the final name of the point in the Excel table is Isosaari20_1953)

Placement criteria for survey points

It is possible to select mapping points in several ways depending on the purpose of the mapping itself. In Velmu, mapping points are divided into different classes (in LajiGIS this is “Sampling Method”). These are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Placement criteria for mapping points.

Randomised (1)	Points are created in the research area based on certain environmental variables (transparency, depth, turbidity, salinity, etc.).
GRID 100 m (2)	A grid is created in the area to be mapped by positioning the points 100 metres apart.
GRID 50 m (3)	A grid is created in the area to be mapped by positioning the points 50 metres apart.
GRID other (4)	A grid is created in the area to be mapped by placing the points at a specified distance. The applied distance must be recorded.
Other than random or GRID (5)	Other placement criteria. For example, mapping surveys based on expert knowledge, i.e. when mapping the occurrences of endangered species.

4. Determining the abiotic properties of the water column and seafloor

The physical and hydrographic measurements of water, such as temperature and salinity, as well as light levels in the water column and the amount of oxygen on the seabed provide the background material for environmental factors affecting the distribution of organisms. Current data are largely based on the monitoring of changes in the state of the marine environment by the environmental administration- and ELY centres. Remote sensing methods can be used to determine various properties, e.g. water turbidity, over the entire Finnish marine area and field measurements play an important role in the calibration and validation of remote sensing evaluations. The collected data will also be used in Velmu to make prediction models for the prevalence of underwater habitats and organisms.

Measuring water transparency using a Secchi disc

The depth measured with a Secchi disc depicts the clarity or turbidity of the water column. Using such water measurements, it is possible to estimate long-term changes in the transparency of the Baltic Sea.

Transparency is measured from all dive lines at the end of the line (100 m end) or from the anchor site when a boat is used to do a dive line. In other surveys, the Secchi depth is measured a few times a day from as many environments as possible. Secchi measurements should only be made in conjunction with mapping points (e.g. video points or dive lines), as measurements without species mapping data cannot be stored in LajiGIS.

To measure transparency, a white metal or plastic plate measuring 30 cm in diameter, or Secchi disc, is attached to a measuring line. The plate should be attached so that it remains horizontal in the water. The measuring line must be made of non-stretchable material and marked at 50 cm intervals from the surface of the plate. Measurements can also be carried out using a Limnos- or other water sampler with a diameter of at least 10 cm. Information about the type of Secchi disk used is always logged in the field protocol.

To measure the Secchi depth, the disc is lowered into the water and the depth at which it disappears from sight is observed. Estimating the depth is facilitated if the disc is raised and lowered at the depth of disappearance. At the same time, the depth is estimated at ± 10 cm of the measurement line at the water surface. Measurements are made when the ship is stationary and on the shaded side of the vessel. Measurements are made only in adequate daylight and in sufficiently calm weather. The measurement results are recorded in the field protocol in conjunction with other data at the sampling point and stored on the Microsoft® Excel LajiGIS marine protocol and later to the LajiGIS information system.

Defining rubbish from dive lines and video points

Dive and video mapping methods detect rubbish on the seafloor. Observations of debris should always be recorded using the various categories listed in Appendix IV and stored in the LajiGIS marine protocol along with other mapping point data.

5. Geological surveys of the seafloor – an overview

The aim of geological field surveys is to collect data on the geological structure of the seafloor from Finnish marine areas. The data collected from the surveyed areas are classified into biologically significant categories for surface sediments and the results are used to build prediction models for the distribution of species and underwater habitats.

Velmu mapping uses the bottom quality classification shown in Table 2.

On dive lines and in video analysis, the percentage of bottom quality classes is estimated so that the total coverage of the different classes sums to exactly 100%. Before fieldwork begins, all those involved in surveys should practice the identification of sediments and particle sizes.

The Geological Survey of Finland (GTK) and the Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE) are also interested in the following seafloor types:

- ✓ Areas where gas is discharged from the seabed
- ✓ Areas with concretions or ferro-manganese deposits
- ✓ Areas with sedimentary rocks such as sandstone and limestone
- ✓ Areas with extensive coverage of the seafloor by mats formed from loose filamentous algae

The location and environmental information of any unique occurrence is recorded and the findings are brought to the attention of GTK and SYKE. Normal occurrences are recorded on the LajiGIS marine protocol and are recorded as usual in LajiGIS information system.

Quantity of loose sediment

The amount of loose sediment observed when using video and dive methods is estimated on a scale of 0-3.

0 = no sediment

1 = little (sediment does not cover plants although small amounts may be detected, particularly on horizontal surfaces of the seafloor).

2 = moderate (sediment is visible on horizontal surfaces and the bottom is easily disturbed. There is also sediment on the surface of aquatic plants).

3 = abundant (loose sediment is plentiful and clearly covers all surfaces).

If for some reason the amount of sediment is not estimated, this field of the LajiGIS marine protocol is left blank.

Table 2. Velmu 2014 Bottom Quality Classification used for dive mapping and video interpretation

Ø Size Class [mm]	Category	Abbreviation	General name (in different grain size classifications)
Solid bedrock	Rock	R	Rock
> 3000 mm	Large boulder	aB	Boulder / Large boulder / Very large boulder
1200 – 3000 mm	Medium boulder	bB	Boulder / Medium boulder / Large boulder
600 – 1200 mm	Small boulder	cB	Boulder / Small boulder
100 – 600 mm	Large stone	aS	Large cobble / Small boulder / Boulder
60 – 100 mm	Small stone	bS	Cobble
2 – 60 mm	Gravel	G	Coarse gravel / Pebble
0,06 – 2,0 mm	Sand	Sa	Coarse sand
0,002 – 0,06 mm	Silt	Si	Silt
< 0,002 mm	Clay	C	Clay
< 0,002 mm	Glacial clay	HC	Hard clay HUB
< 0,002 mm	Mud	M	Mud

Specialised categories:

Ø Size class [mm]	Category	Abbreviation	General name (in different grain size classifications)
Variable	Concretions of iron/manganese	Cr	Concretions / ferro-manganese deposits or nodules
Variable	Sandstone	Ss	Sandstone
Variable	Artificial substrates	Ar	Artificial substrate / Manmade structures
Variable	Peat	Pe	Peat
Variable	Tree trunks/branches	Tr	Tree trunks/branches

6. Velmu Priority Species: rare, endangered, poorly known and alien species

One of the aims of the Velmu surveys is to provide detailed information on the prevalence of rare and endangered species, as well as poorly known and invasive species in Finnish sea areas. The species listed below are priority species in Velmu and it is important to identify them whenever possible. In particular, the identification of priority species should be learned and reviewed before the beginning of the field season.

All fish observations must also always be recorded and entered into the Excel/LajiGIS.

For further questions about invasive, fish species species and general species identification, please contact Maiju Lehtiniemi (maiju.lehtiniemi@syke.fi) and Sanna Kuningas (sanna.kuningas@luke.fi), Mats Westerbom (mats.westerbom@luke.fi) and Lari Veneranta (lari.veneranta@luke.fi).

Identification levels of plants, algae and animal species

For underwater vegetation, identification is almost always made to species level. Special attention is paid to Velmu's priority species, and observations are always confirmed by taking a sample where possible. Due to the prioritisation of resources, the most important biological species groups for Velmu, in particular priority species, are always accurately identified (time is used for species identification in the laboratory) and many samples are taken. Specifically, terrestrial species, i.e. those not included in the aquatic environment, such as trees, grasses, etc., those not mentioned in the attached species table are not identified to species if the analysis work requires extra working time.

The surveyor should be aware of the limits of both the regional and depth distribution of a species. Particular care must be taken in species identification and confirmation where the observations are deeper or shallower than the normal growth depth range, including observations at both the extremes of and beyond their normal range. In such cases, it is also appropriate to provide a sample of these unusual findings to species experts.

Divers should concentrate on observing small-sized species and other plants and algae that are difficult to detect using other sampling methods. In particular, for species groups that are poorly known and difficult to identify, a large number of samples should be taken and the samples retained for subsequent identification. Well-preserved samples can be delivered to Luomus (The Finnish Museum of Natural History), along with their associated logged metadata from the LajiGIS marine protocol. Alternatively, several experts should be involved in the identification process.

Species identification levels can be broadly divided as follows:

Species level (always where possible)

Velmu priority species
Macroalgae
Charophytes
Aquatic Bryophytes
Floating-, submerged- and bottom-leaved aquatic plants
Aerial shoot plants

Genus or family level if the determination to species level is slow

Woody plants
Grasses
Shoreline plants
Oligochaete worms (from benthic samples)
Chironomid larvae (from benthic samples)

General remark

In dive surveys, it is not generally appropriate to attempt to identify species using a method poorly suited to the task, particularly when better means are used for mapping. For example, small-sized invertebrates from hard sea bottoms are better determined using Kautsky-square samples, rather than being solely based on diver observations.

Taxonomic linking

A hierarchical system has been built into the Excel input table to indicate the accuracy of a species observation when full certainty about its identification has not been obtained, e.g. through the interpretation of video material or species identification otherwise based solely on visual observation. Recording the correct observation accuracy significantly increases the reliability of the entire survey data. The surveyor should be aware of the level of species identification in each observation column, so it is a good idea to become familiar with how the hierarchy of observations are entered before starting any field surveys.

The “Species Names” tab of the Excel data input sheet provides instructions about the accuracy with which observations are recorded in each aggregation group column. Below are examples of the hierarchy of observational accuracy for different species groups.

1. Taxonomic hierarchy:

Chara baltica var. *breviaculeata* -> *Chara baltica* -> *Chara* sp. -> Charales -> Macrophyte

At the species level, only individuals that grow clearly on the bottom or on the surface of other species are marked, and plant specimens detached from their substrate are not marked as a live species observation (except for free-floating and, for example, loose-growing, living *Fucus vesiculosus* or deep-rooted *Coccotylus truncatus*/*Phyllophora pseudoceranoides*). Masses of plant material accumulated on the bottom or loose, floating macrophytes are labeled as “Drifting macrophytes” or “Drifting unidentified plant material”, despite the fact that live, identifiable vascular plants are visible.

Zannichellia palustris var. *pedicellata* -> *Zannichellia palustris* -> *Zannichellia* sp. -> Vascular plants -> Macrophyte -> **plant detaches from the bottom at this point** -> Drifting macrophyte -> Drifting unidentified plant material

2. In the case of similar looking species, collective groups shall be used if more accurate species identification is not available:

Chara/Nitella

Myriophyllum sp./*Ceratophyllum* sp.

Coccolytus / *Phyllophora* / *Furcellaria*

Pot pect/Pot fili/*Ruppia* sp./*Zannichellia* sp.

3. In case that similar looking species occur as common alien species within a marine area, a group identifier shall be used for the observed species, unless a precise species identification has been carried out:

Mytilus trossulus -> *Mytilus* / *Mytilopsis* / *Dreissena*

4. In the absence of more precise species identification, filamentous algae shall be grouped together:

Ceramium tenuicorne -> *Ceramium* sp. -> Attached red filamentous algae -> Attached unidentified filamentous algae </> 5cm -> Filamentous algae (if it cannot be seen whether attached or loose) -> **filamentous algae detach from the substrate at this point** -> Drifting filamentous algae -> Drifting macrophyte -> Drifting unidentified plant material

Ectocarpus siliculosus -> *Pilayella littoralis* / *Ectocarpus siliculosus* -> Attached brown filamentous algae -> Attached unidentified filamentous algae </> 5 cm -> Filamentous algae (if it cannot be seen whether attached or loose) -> **filamentous algae detach from the substrate at this point** -> Drifting filamentous algae -> Drifting macrophyte -> Drifting unidentified plant material

5. How to label bladderwrack (*Fucus*):

Fucus vesiculosus -> *Fucus* sp. -> **macroalgae detaches from the bottom at this point** -> Drifting *Fucus* (alive) -> Drifting *Fucus* (dead) sp. -> Drifting macrophyte -> Drifting unidentified plant material

Live bladder wrack fragments growing on soft bottoms are labelled *Fucus vesiculosus* + soft bottom quality and marked in the bottom quality columns. "Soft bottom living *Fucus*" is marked in the comment box.

In marine areas where two *Fucus* species occur: *Fucus vesiculosus* or *Fucus radicans* -> *Fucus* sp.

Endangered and priority species

Endangered macrophytes are recorded in addition to other species information

“Description of the observation site” and “Description of the observation”, for example:

Description of the observation site: "South of Sandö Island, a large rock on the shore."

Description of the observation: "Approximately 1 m² of vegetation growth on a rock."

In addition, the number of individuals of endangered species in the sample area is recorded, even if the percentage coverage is recorded.

Fish

Fish are always recorded as numbers of individuals (adult/juvenile). The number of individuals in fish shoals and schools of small fish may be estimated and noted in the remarks as “fish shoal” or “small fish”.

Threatened species

- Spined Loach (*Cobitis taenia*) (NT)
- Two-spotted Goby (*Gobiusculus flavescens*) (NT)
- Black Goby (*Gobius niger*) (NT)
- Burbot (*Lota lota*) (NT)
- Flounder (*Platichthys flesus*) (NT)
- Fifteen-spined Stickleback (*Spinachia spinachia*) (NT)
- Grayling (*Thymallus thymallus*) (CR, In the Baltic Sea)

Poorly known species

- Snake Blenny (*Lumpenus lampretaeformis*) (DD)
- Striped Sea-snail (*Liparis liparis*) (DD)
- Short-horn Sculpin (*Myoxocephalus scorpius*) (DD)
- Sichel (*Pelecus cultratus*) (LC)
- Garfish (*Belone belone*) (LC)
- Turbot (*Scophthalmus maximus*) (DD)
- Long-spined Bullhead (*Taurulus bubalis*) (DD)
- Butterfish (*Pholis gunnellus*) (DD)

Alien Species

- Round Goby (*Apollonia* [*Neogobius*] *melanostomus*)
- Silver Prussian Carp (*Carassius auratus m. gibelio*)

Recording the spawning observations of fish

It is important to record the spawning observations of fish to support modelling of the spawning area. In some species, spawning can be recorded as a species-specific observation. For example, the spawning ribbons of perch or the spawning eggs of herring that extensively cover both the sea bottom and vegetation alike. If the species cannot be determined, the taxon *Pisces* is used. Spawning is recorded in the species identification data of the marine Excel form using the Quantity Unit code 14 (egg). The

field observations describes the number and extent of spawn, e.g. the number of spawning ribbos of perch. In addition, photos of the spawn will help to later confirm the species identification.

Invertebrates

Threatened species

Marine Leaf Beetle (*Macrolea pubipennis*) (NT)
Sea-slug (*Alderia modesta*) (NT)

Poorly known species

River Snails (*Viviparus contectus* ja *Viviparus viviparus*)
Lake Leaf Beetle (*Macrolea appendiculata*)

Alien species

Harris Mudcrab (*Rhithropanopeus harrisi*)
Grass Prawn (*Palaemon elegans*)
Amphipod (*Gammarus tigrinus*)
Zebra mussel (*Dreissena polymorpha*)
Dark False Mussel (*Mytilopsis leucophaeata*)
Chinese Mitten Crab (*Eriocheir sinensis*)
Murchisonellidae gastropods

Gulf Wedge-Clam (*Rangia cuneata*)
Non-indigenous tanaid crustacean (*Sinelobus vanhaareni*)

Plants and Algae

Threatened species

(*Ceramium virgatum*) (VU)
Straggly Bush Weed (*Rhodomela confervoides*) (NT)
(*Dictyosiphon chordaria*) (NT)
Bladder wrack (*Fucus vesiculosus*) (NT)
(*F. radicans*) (NT)
Spiny Naiad (*Najas tenuissima*) (EN)
Many-branched Stonewort (*Nitella hyalina*) (VU)
Knotweed (*Persicaria foliosa*) (EN)
Four-leaved Mare's Tail (*Hippuris tetraphylla*) (VU)
Flat-stalked Pondweed (*Potamogeton friesii*) (NT)
Bristly Stonewort (*Chara horrida*) (EN)
Braun's Stonewort (*Chara braunii*) (VU)

Starry Stonewort (*Nitellopsis obtusa*) (NT)
Baltic Water-plantain (*Alisma wahlenbergii*) (VU)
Pigmyweed (*Crassula aquatica*) (VU)

Poorly known species

Landlady's Wig (*Ahnfeltia plicata*) (DD)
Battersia plumigera (DD)
Blidingia minima (DD)
Capsosiphon fulvescens (DD)
Chaetomorpha linum (DD)
Chaetophora lobata (DD)
Stalked Leaf Bearer/*Coccotylus truncatus* (DD)
Grania efflorescens (DD)
Halopteris scoparia (DD)
Furry Rope Weed *Halosiphon tomentosus* (DD)
Leathesia marina (DD)
Monostroma grevillei (DD)
Percursaria percursa (DD)
Phyllophora pseudoceranooides (DD)
Discoïd Forked Weed (*Polyides rotunda*) (DD)
Prasiola crispa (DD)
Prasiola furfuracea (DD)
Prasiola stipitata (DD)
Protohalopteris radicans (DD)
Pseudolithoderma extensum (DD)
Pseudolithoderma rosenvingei (DD)
Pseudolithoderma subextensum (DD)
Punctaria tenuissima (DD)
Rhizoclonium riparium (DD)
Rosenvingiella polyrhiza (DD)
Scytosiphon lomentaria (DD)
Sphacelorbis nanus (DD)
Spongomorpha aeruginosa (DD)
Ulothrix flacca (DD)
Ulothrix subflaccida (DD)
Ulothrix tenerrima (DD)
Ulva clathrata (DD)
Ulva flexuosa (DD)
Ulva linza (DD)
Ulva prolifera (DD)
Urospora penicilliformis (DD)
Vaucheria intermedia (DD)
Vaucheria litorea (DD)
Vaucheria synandra (DD)

In addition to macroalgae, vernal- and water's edge species

Alien species

Canadian waterweed (*Elodea canadensis*)

Other priority species

Red Clubrush (*Blysmopsis rufa*)
Flat-sedge (*Blysmus compressus*)
Lance-leaved Mare's Tail (*Hippuris lanceolata*)
Beaked tasselweed (*Ruppia maritima*)
Spiral tasselweed (*Ruppia spiralis*)
Sea Pearlwort (*Sagina maritima*)
Glasswort (*Salicornia perennans*)
Seaside Brookweed (*Samolus valerandi*)

Alien species

Canadian Pondweed (*Elodea canadensis*)

Other priority species

Red Clubrush (*Blysmopsis rufa*)
Flat Sedge (*Blysmus compressus*)
Mare's-Tail (*Hippuris lanceolata*)
Beaked Tasselweed (*Ruppia maritima*)
Spiral Tasselweed (*Ruppia spiralis*)
Sea Pearlwort (*Sagina maritima*)
Glasswort (*Salicornia perennans*)
Seaside Brookweed (*Samolus valerandi*)

Identification of benthic fauna observed from dives and videos

<i>Anodonta anatina</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Aurelia aurita</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Amphibalanus improvisus</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Cerastoderma/Macoma baltica/Mya arenaria</i> shells	Percentage coverage
<i>Cordylophora caspia</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Crangon crangon</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Dreissena polymorpha</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Electra crustulenta</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Embletonia pallida</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Ephydatia fluviatilis</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Galerucella nymphaea</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Hydra</i> sp.	Percentage coverage

<i>Laomeda loveni</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Macoma baltica</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Macrophea</i> spp.	Number of individuals
<i>Mya arenaria</i>	Percentage coverage
Mysidae	Presence/Estimated number
<i>Mytilopsis leucophaeata</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Mytilus trossulus</i> x <i>edulis</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Mytilus trossulus/edulis</i> crushed shell	Percentage coverage
<i>Palaemon adspersus</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Palaemon elegans</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Saduria entomon</i>	Number of individuals
<i>Spongilla lacustris</i>	Percentage coverage
<i>Unio</i> spp.	Number of individuals
<i>Viviparus contectus</i>	Number of individuals

7. Transect Surveys

At shallow depths of approximately zero to twenty metres, accurate species mapping is carried out by scuba diving or by comparable methods, such as snorkelling or wading using an Aquascope. The choice of these methods is indicated by the depth and bottom quality, e.g. wading is only successful on suitably hard rocky or sandy bottoms at appropriately shallow depths.

If a biological surveyor can take samples from the bottom while floating on the surface, the survey point can be carried out by snorkelling. Conversely, if a snorkeller has difficulty seeing the bottom or being able to reach it, they must switch to using scuba equipment. Free diving from the surface to the bottom does not produce reliable species assessments and sampling is also impossible.

When designing vegetation surveys, the seasonal development of species should be taken into account: many annual filamentous algae are only observable at the peak of their life cycle, while the abundance of some aquatic plants can only be estimated at the end of the summer, i.e. at the end of the growing season. Therefore, vegetation mapping of the shoreline zones can produce very different results in different seasons (Ruuskanen *et al.* 2002). As a result, biological surveys are usually performed at the height of the growing season when both algae and aquatic plants are well represented. The timing of this period varies between north and south and should be taken into account when planning the survey. In general, although the peak of the growing season is reached in July-August, the growth peak and species variety may vary between habitats. For species typical of lagoons and gloe lakes, the most representative period occurs from July to August. Similarly, August is the most favourable survey time for the sandy beaches of outer archipelagos, while on rocky shores, perennial algae are most easily detected only in August-September. However, planning surveyors must also take into account that selecting the time of the maximum growth will omit some of the early season species completely from their assessments.

Vegetation transect

Vegetation lines or transects laid out perpendicular to the beach produce the most comprehensive data on the variety of the survey area and the relationship between species at different depths (Niemi 1990). Transect mapping is done as follows:

1. Laying out a line

A weighted measuring tape or rope marked at metre intervals is extended perpendicularly from the waterline by boat and lowered to the sea bed (Fig. 2). A coloured surface buoy is attached to the deep end of the tape or rope, which allows the diver to descend directly to the deepest part of the transect line. While the line can also be drawn out by diving, this is not recommended because it extends the dive time and increases the diver's air consumption and physical exertion. Moreover, the straightness of the transect line may suffer. However, diving the line out is justified in situations where the boat cannot get close to the planned starting point of the vegetation line, due to excessive rockiness or shallowness of the shoreline. A diver

can also swim on the surface to take the line to its starting point on the shore while simultaneously taking its GPS coordinates, after which the line can be drawn out by boat.

- ✓ The end of the transect at the water's edge is always designated as the line's starting point (0 m). The transect may also have its starting and ending points in open water, e.g. on a reef.
- ✓ A vegetation mapping transect always ends at 20 metres depth or at 100 metres from the shoreline, depending on which criterion is fulfilled first.

Fig. 1. Schematic of a shoreline diving transect. © Metsähallitus / Suvi Saarnio

2. Determining the location and direction of the line

The coordinates of the start and end points of the line are recorded to a GPS device at the waterline or at the start (0 m) and end buoys (100 m). On the shore, the start point coordinate should be taken when the weight is cast to the waterline and the end point coordinate when lowering the 100 m buoy. The diver determines the compass direction of the dive line from the dive startpoint (0 m) on the shore towards the buoy at the end of the line, with an accuracy of ten degrees (as a number from 0-360°). The same method is also used for dive lines placed in open water.

3. Beginning the dive

The diver descends to the deepest end of the dive line or pulls it out to 100 meters, but only to a maximum vertical depth of 20 meters. If the end of the line calculated from the boat is more than 20 meters deep, the diver will swim immediately to a depth of 20 meters on the dive line, where the first quadrat estimation is made.

4. Defining the quadrat estimation

After arriving on the line, the biological surveyor evaluates the amount and quality of vegetation in the first quadrat.

The percent coverage estimates are made within a four square metre rectangle or quadrat extending two metres laterally on both sides of the line and one metre upwards (Fig. 3). While the surveyor can use their own height or the maximum distance of their spread arms as an approximate measure for the quadrat assessment, they must have measured the dimensions of their body beforehand to ensure that the correct area of the bottom is examined. In addition, the bottom slope is estimated in degrees from 0 to 90 degrees, where 0° is horizontal and 90° is vertical (Fig. 4).

Quadrats are made along the entire transect, either at intervals of one or ten metres, depending on which condition is met from the first quadrat to the next. In addition, a new quadrat is always done when the bottom quality, key species, or habitat type clearly changes, e.g. when the bottom quality moves from sandy to rocky or when the bottom vegetation changes from vascular plants to one dominated by reeds.

If the quadrat is placed at a point [Z; X], where Z is the vertical depth in metres and X is the distance along the dive line in metres, the criteria for placing the next quadrat on the line is either:

- i. to a point [Z-1; x] with $X-10 < x < X$, i.e. where the vertical depth decreases by 1 m before proceeding 10 m along the line or,
- ii. to a point [z; X-10] with a depth of $Z-1 < z < Z$, i.e. where the diver must travel 10 meters along the dive without the vertical depth changing by 1 m or,
- iii. to a point [z; x], where the depth = $Z-1 < z < Z$ and the distance on the dive line is equal to $X-10 < x < X$, i.e. where the bottom quality or habitat type changes clearly before the depth or distance criteria (i and ii) are met.

Thus, quadrats are made at horizontal intervals of at least ten meters, for each one metre decrease in vertical depth and in some cases more frequently. When the ground quality or habitat type show clear changes along the dive line, an evaluation quadrat is made immediately for the new bottom type, regardless of whether the above depth or distance conditions (i.e. depth change of 1 m or a 10 m progression along on line from the previous quadrat) are still met.

All estimation quadrats are made according to the same logic. However, the last quadrat on the line is made as shallow as safely possible, such that the last frame is made at the water line (i.e. at distance of 1 m if the 0 m end of the measuring line is at the water's edge).

At the last quadrat, the distance (in metres) of the transect's 0 m point to the mean water limit (referred to in the LajiGIS field protocol as "Distance of transect from shore") is estimated. If the end of the transect does not reach the waterline, e.g. the distance to the shoreline is five metres, additional quadrats can be made up to the water line, continuing from 0 m on the transect using negative distance measurements. Thus, quadrats made at the starting point of the line (0 m) toward the shore are recorded as negative distances (for example -5 m on the transect). This makes it easy to calculate these intermediate coordinates. Those distances measured from the end of the transect are not corrected as distances from the water's edge, instead offshore shoreward quadrats are only added to the quadrats made on the transect using negative distances.

If it has not appeared on the deepest quadrat, the vertical depth and transect distance at which the deepest algae or plant species is growing is also written on the field protocol.

The aim is to identify all macroscopic species (especially priority species) that can be identified while doing the biological survey, and to gain an overview of the biological community on the transect. While each quadrat should be searched to find as many species as possible, the species coverage estimates can still be done quickly, as it is not necessary to go through the screen precisely to determine the coverage of each species present.

Fig. 3. Transect quadrat. The quadrat is always evaluated perpendicularly (at an angle of 90 degrees to the bottom surface). On a steep seafloor, the bottom gradient is also estimated in degrees ranging from 0° to 90°, where 0° is horizontal and 90° is vertical).

Fig.4. Gradient examples ranging from 0 to 90 degrees.

5. Observations made at each quadrat

- The distance in metres from the starting point of the dive line to the bottom of the quadrat (i.e. "distance on transect").
- The depth in metres at the lower edge of the quadrat.
- The percent coverages (summing to 100%) for Velmu bottom quality categories (Table 1). The amount of loose sediment on the seabed is also assessed on a scale from 0 to 3 (Chapter 5). The number and types of rubbish are recorded according to their categories in the corresponding Microsoft® Excel file. The bottom gradient is estimated in degrees from 0-90°; 0° = horizontal surface, 90° = vertical surface).
- Estimations are made of the percent coverage of aquatic plants and macroalgae from the whole quadrat, either as total coverage for the area or by substrate specific type (there is a separate method for each approach), and the average height of species. The percent cover of epiphytic algae, i.e. algae growing on other plants, is evaluated relative to the entire quadrat area. If the species is on the red list, also the number of individuals is written down.

For all species where underwater identification is not entirely certain, the surveyor will take a sample and record the sampling container number, in addition to the coverage of the species (see example below). Since a large proportion of species require microscopy, a sufficient number of samples must be collected from the assessment quadrats to ensure a sufficiently accurate species identification. In particular, filamentous macroalgae and water mosses must almost always be identified under a microscope.

Sometimes it is impossible to determine the species coverage within the assessment quadrat. In such cases, presence data can be used instead. The value for presence data is set to 0.001. For all species, the smallest possible percent coverage value is 0.1%.

- The abundance of sessile animals attached to the substratum within the quadrat is estimated as either as total percent coverage, in the same manner as macrophytes, or as numbers of individuals. Their heights are not evaluated. Different assay methods for different animal species are presented in Chapter 6.

- f. The upper and lower limits of bladder wrack are recorded where such a zone occurs on or near the dive line. Bladder wrack is considered to form a zone if it covers more than 30% of the quadrat. In addition, the depths of the deepest and shallowest occurring individuals present in the zone are written in the dive protocol.

If necessary, a zone description can also be recorded for a bladder wrack zone.

- g. **All fish species are identified and recorded as numbers of individuals (see Chapter 6),** but only if the individuals can be identified to species or genus level.

6. Immediately after the biological survey

The surveyor writes a brief general description of the transect and the surrounding area. This description is saved to the LajiGIS column "Survey observations".

- a. General state of the habitat
- b. Detectable signs of eutrophication
- c. Key species/dominant species on or close to the dive line
- d. Shoreline land use
- e. Littering
- f. Traces/damage left behind from human activity and their extent.

In addition, when encountering threatened species, additional information will be recorded, such as:

"Site description" and "Description of the observation". For example:

Site description: "South of Sandö Island, east of a large rock on the shallow shore"

Description of the observation: "1 m² patch of vegetation growth on rock"

7. Saving and modifying data

- Transect line depth data are recorded as measured depths. Sub- and above-surface depths are assigned positive and negative values, respectively.
- The daily mean sea level in the area is recorded in metres in the LajiGIS field protocol (no correction is calculated at this stage). A water level height above the mean is denoted as a positive value and below as a negative value.
- The transect quadrat surface area of 4 m² is recorded (Note! LajiGIS code 16). In shallow bays, the quadrat surface area may also be 1 m² (Note! LajiGIS code 14) (see LajiGIS codes, Appendix III)
- The person who made the species identification is included in the species information. If the species sample has been sent for identification to an external expert, care must be taken that the species identification information will be corrected later (including the name of the person who made the identification).

- Observations made from outside the assessment quadrats themselves or close to the transect are recorded in the LajiGIS excel file column “General observations by diving (28)”.
- Examples of the field protocols used in Velmu inventories are provided in the appendices.

Making a transect on shallow even bottoms

The transect instructions mentioned above apply to all diving, snorkelling and wading lines with minor exceptions. It is important to collect consistent material regardless of how the transect is implemented.

Depending on the depth and visibility, vegetation lines are carried out by either diving/snorkelling, wading with an Aquascope, and taking samples with a rake. The vegetation is evaluated by quadrats placed every 10 metres, with a surface area of 1 m² or 4 m², depending on the vegetation abundance and the water clarity. In bays with abundant flora, the vegetation often grows in layers, and both species numbers and coverage may be very high. Mapping with a wider quadrat area under such conditions is very slow and inaccurate, so the 1 m² quadrat size can be used instead if necessary. The quadrat area used for each assessment is logged. In all other respects, the instructions follow the vegetation transect guidelines described above.

If a lagoon has a large surface area and/or very sparse vegetation, replacing some of the assessment quadrats in the centre using random video- or divepoints can be considered. When performing individual mapping points, a sufficient number should be assessed in order to detect potential different habitats in the middle of the bay under study.

Placing transects in shallow bays

In shallow and even areas beyond bays, the placement of the vegetation line is carried out as described above for deeper sites. Mapping begins by extending a theoretical line from the innermost part of the bay to its mouth. This line is used to support the placement of the actual mapping lines. These lines are drawn at an angle of about 90 degrees to the initial line so that each mapping line extends from the shoreline across the bay. The first and innermost line is made in as shallow water as possible at the water's edge or where reeds meet the open water. Depending on the length of the bay, the following lines are positioned 25 to 100 metres apart, with the aim of covering the various parts of the bay as carefully as possible. The last mapping line should be located at the narrowest and shallowest part of the bay opening, where water flow is often strong and thus the bottom quality is often different from the rest of the bay (Figure 5). The indicative locations of the lines can be planned beforehand, for example, using aerial photographs. Random video or dive points can also be placed on vegetation patches that are not covered by the mapping lines. This will ensure the broadest possible species mapping of the entire bay.

Fig. 5. Placement of theoretical planning lines (black) in an example bay. On the left, the red dots show the intersection of the mapping line on the planning line. Additional planning lines can be placed in the area as needed. The vegetation lines are shown on the right in red.

An example box from a transect quadrat

Depth 2,4 m

Distance on the line 17 m

Bedrock (R) 20 %, small stone (bS) 10 %, gravel (G) 10 % and sand (Sa) 60 %, no loose sediment, quadrat gradient 30 degrees.

Bladder wrack (*Fucus vesiculosus*) is approximately 20 cm high and covers 15% of the quadrat. Mermaid's hair algae (*Cladophora glomerata*) covers 10 % of the the quadrat (some grows underneath the bladderwrack) measuring aproximately 10 cm in height. Perfoliate pondweed (*Potamogeton perfoliatus*) grows to 50 cm, with a coverage of 5 % on both gravel and sand. Red pearl algae (*Ceramium tenuicorne*) covers 1 % and grows to 5 cm in height. Blue mussels (*Mytilus trossulus*) have a coverage of 10 %. In addition, two specimens of large isopod (*Saduria entomon*) were spotted, along with a poorly defined amount of tufted seamoss (*Cladophora rupestris*).

In the case of the above example, the surveyor would write it as follows:

17 / 2,4: Sed 0, Gradient 30. R20, bS10, G10, Sa60, Fucves 15/20, Certen 1/5, Claglo 10/10 (X4), Clarup 0,001 (X5), Potper 5/50 (X6), Myttro 10, Sadent 2,

While doing the vegetation survey, the surveyor would collect plant and algae samples in sample jars, e.g. mermaid's hair algae in X4, tufted seamoss in X5 and perfoliate pondweed in X6. Based on the species identifications made from the samples, corrections (when needed) are made to the surveying protocol before saving to the LajiGIS marine protocol in Microsoft® Excel.

Transect overview: an example

A concise description is written for each dive line and saved to LajiGIS under the heading "Mapping observations".

- a. General state of the habitat
- b. Detectable signs of eutrophication
- c. Key species/ dominant species on or close to the dive line
- d. Shoreline land use

- e. Littering
- f. Traces / damage left behind from human activity and their extent.

For example, the general description could be as follows:

a. Sheltered and shallow bay appears to be in satisfactory condition with diverse vegetation. Water visibility is approximately one metre. b. There is a lot of loose sediment on plants, as well as annual filamentous algae. The bottom has organic material and the mud smells of rotten eggs. c. There are a lot of reeds and bulrushes near the shoreline. The central parts of the bay are dominated by spiny naiads and yellow water lillies. d. There are plenty of summer cottages and fixed pier structures around the line. There are no roads, rivers or fields closeby. There is a small marina and restaurant about 500 m distant. e. There was no rubbish observed either in the water or on the shore. f. The bay has been dredged from the docks to the mouth of the bay and the reeds have been mown from both the cottage and marina areas.

8. Point surveys or wading

In addition to precise coordinates (start point coordinates only), the same information is collected at a survey point or a wading point as at a transect. Hence, point surveying is a special case of a transect in which there is only a single assessment quadrat.

When a sample point is assessed as a single point, the sampling area of 4 m² can also be surveyed as a 2x2 m square. For example, using an Aquascope, it is useful to look approximately one metre in all directions either while standing on the bottom (if the bottom is hard and not easily disturbed) or from a SUP board (if the bottom is soft).

9. Mapping of targeted and endangered species by diving or wading

It is not efficient to map poorly known or endangered species along such transects outlined above. Instead, mapping is usually done by diving/snorkelling or wading parallel to the shore and searching for the target species.

In connection with mapping, the following shall be recorded:

i. point surveys at all points, where the target species is detected

- ✓ point survey = a single quadrat with all data

- ✓ The location of each quadrat is saved as its own waypoint. For each quadrat, be sure to enter the name of the waypoint from the GPS device on the dive protocol!
- ✓ Endangered macrophytes are recorded in addition to other species information

In addition to other data, when encountering threatened species, additional information will be recorded, e.g.

“Site description” and “Description of the observation”. For example:

Site description “South of Sandö Island, east of the large rock on the shallow shore”

Description of the observation: “1 m² vegetation patch on rock”

In addition to % coverage, the number of individuals should be recorded.

- ✓ **A general overview** of the sampling site is recorded for all sampling quadrats
 - a. General state of the habitat
 - b. Detectable signs of eutrophication
 - c. Key species/ dominant species on or close to the dive line
 - d. Shoreline land use
 - e. Littering
 - f. Traces / damage left behind from human activity and their extent.
- ii. **The route stored on the GPS device from the mapped area** (to describe the area that was mapped).
 - ✓ The following information is stored in connection with the route to be saved in GPX format: Species to be mapped, surveyor’s name, site name, and the survey date

Spatial information is collected from both the route travelled and the observations made. Therefore, in order to define the route, the diver must carry a GPS device set to automatically record the track taken. All target species observations are recorded as waypoints on GPS and the field protocol. The route travelled or area mapped are stored separately on a local hard disk in the spatial data format (GPX) and not on the LajiGIS marine protocol, unlike the mapping points. The data is compiled at the end of the field season and transferred to LajiGIS. It is important to remember to name the files and waypoints so that the information can be linked to the right mapping event.

Along with targeted species mapping, dive points should also be carried out for sites with zero observations. These dive points are evaluated and biota recorded in all assessment quadrants according to the dive line methodology.

10. Biological survey equipment

- ✓ A GPS device to determine coordinates at the mapping location

- ✓ Appropriate and properly serviced diving equipment
- ✓ Sinking, non-stretch tape or rope with a length of at least 100 m
- ✓ A weight, surface rope and buoy must be attached to the end of the rope or measuring tape
- ✓ A writing disc with attached
 - Pencil and spare pen
 - Diving protocol printed on waterproof paper
- ✓ Sampling equipment
 - Forceps / knife
 - Numbered jars or bottles for small samples
 - Numbered collection bags for large samples
- ✓ A waterproof light for conditions of low visibility, darkness and depths of more than 10 m.
- ✓ Knife, or cutter for emergencies when diving as a pair.
- ✓ Tools for single-point mapping: an Aquascope (water telescope), SUP-board, anchor and rake.

11. Underwater Video

Underwater video filming is suitable for mapping large coastal areas and for the rapid collection of information at the community level. This method is also well suited for mapping the occurrence and regional limits of important habitat-forming key species such as bladder wrack, vascular plants and blue mussels.

Although the advantages of video recording include both speed and cost-effectiveness for mapping large areas and habitats, it is poorly suited for a comprehensive species level review. Using video to observe algae and plants of different sizes, which may overlap and change in appearance, is often impossible from video footage. In practice, only a few large species can be safely identified from video and therefore, a more complete biological mapping must be done by diving. Nevertheless, the benefit of video is that it saves a visual record that can be reviewed.

Drop-video

Drop-video involves recording underwater video from a boat, filming mainly from predetermined points. This method records short videos of about one minute in length. The field inventory team consists of two or three persons: one to drive the boat, a second to operate the camera, and a third acting as a dat logger/navigator. The quality assurance of the material begins with a prepared plan, followed by the correctly performed activity in the field. High quality and steady video is the foundation for successful video interpretation, while a low quality video sequence may not be saved even by a skilled analyst. Thus, video filming is always done under the most favorable conditions. In heavy seas, currents, poor visibility, or otherwise difficult conditions, it is not advisable to film as it directly affects the video quality.

The success of each filming event must be ensured by the adequate training and practice of the field team. In addition to the weather, good results are influenced by favourable environmental conditions for filming, the skills of the boat driver and the performance of the camera operator. Good control of the practical performance of video recording is an important part of the process because poorly filmed videos cause erroneous or incomplete video interpretations and thus, undermine the reliability and usability of the material. Failed videos are a waste of resources, therefore from the outset, attention must be paid to proper performance in the field, as well as the quality of the camera equipment. The final product of the video method is not only the analysis made from the material but also the video sequence itself, which can be reviewed later. For this reason, it is worth investing in high quality video footage.

In addition, reliable filming equipment and the quality of the video it shoots are key to producing high quality material. All camera models need a sufficiently powerful and wide floodlight system to illuminate the seabed. In order to acquire the surface area of the bottom being filmed by the camera, it is necessary to know the camera lens characteristics, as well as the magnitude of the field of view in degrees. To determine the size of objects, it is recommended to install parallel laser pointers on the camera, so that the laser light points

in the footage are spaced apart by a known distance, thereby giving a size reference for the objects filmed.

After arriving at the mapping location, the boat's motion is stopped and the camera is lowered to the bottom. Using a surface monitor with live video feed allows the operator to follow in real time as the camera approaches the sea floor. Video recording begins when the bottom comes into view and the camera movement is steady. As recording begins, the start coordinates and depth (to an accuracy of 0.5 m) are also logged in the video protocol.

Good quality footage of the seabed lasting at least one minute is recorded for each point. With the help of both general and close-up footage, the goal is to create an overall understanding of each inventory point as a habitat. During filming, the aim is to keep the boat as stationary as possible so that the video captures exactly the area of that inventory point.

The camera should point slightly downwards at an angle of approximately 45 degrees, depending on the camera type used. Sufficient lighting should be employed, particularly in deep areas in order to properly distinguish the details and colours of the underwater landscape. To ensure the quality of the video footage, the camera operator should be able to see live video footage via a surface monitor, thereby allowing them to control the distance of the camera from the bottom. At some point during the video, before the recording is finished, the camera is allowed to knock gently on the seabed. This allows the evaluation of the quality of soft bottoms and to detect the presence of loose sediment. Such contact may kick up fine sediments, thereby giving additional information of bottom quality.

After one minute of good quality video, the recording is stopped and the final coordinates and video depth are logged. It should be noted that this depth reading is never completely correct, because both the depth sensor and the filming position will be located at different points in the boat, depending on the type used. However, the location of the transducer can be calibrated before the field season so that the echo position is automatically taken into account at the displayed depth. In addition, the ID and time of the recorded video is logged for each video point. The Secchi depth is also measured periodically during the day from the video points and these measurements are saved to their specific point.

For each filming day, background information, such as the name of the boat and the inventory team members, as well as the environmental conditions, e.g. sea level and temperature, etc., are logged. Other noteworthy observations that may affect the video, such as wind speed and direction, strong algal blooms or pollen are also recorded daily.

In the field, all video information is recorded in the video protocol, from which the data is transferred to the LajiGIS marine protocol when interpreting the videos. When shooting in an open boat, it is advisable to copy the video protocol onto water-resistant paper and to make as clear notes as possible to facilitate transcription afterwards.

After each filming day, all videos, waypoints stored in the GPS device, and field protocols should be backed up on a hard disc drive and named according to the protocol. Completed protocols can also be backed up in the field using photography.

Remotely Operated Underwater Vehicle - ROV

The ROV unit is a submersible vehicle which incorporates a camera and can film long lines or circuits lasting from 10 to 30 minutes. It is manually controlled from the surface using a control unit, via a surface monitor. The ROV device must have a positioning system to provide continuous coordinate information from the line or other pattern driven, which can be incorporated to the video footage.

Although an ROV has increased space and energy demands and usually requires larger vessels, it is also possible to use smaller boats as long as they have a power source. Typically, ROV operation and filming requires three people: one is responsible for cable feed and recovery, the second is an assistant/data logger and the third operates the ROV itself. The task of the cable operator is to inform the ROV operator of potential problems, so that the cable can either be wound in or the motion of the ROV itself can be controlled to avoid the cable running into the propellers. The assistant records the observations made during the run and the operator is responsible for the ROV control and video filming.

As with drop video, the end use of the material to be collected should also be considered when using ROV. Videos should be shot close enough to the bottom and at a sufficiently slow pace to make subsequent video analysis as easy as possible. After each run, the video and location files must be named according to the research point and backup copies of the video material should be handled properly.

Video interpretation

Based on a one minute video, video interpretation aims to determine an inventory point's habitat as reliably as possible. The abundance of individual- or groups of organisms is estimated as a percent coverage over the whole minute. If the vegetation is layered, the sum of the total coverage of the different species may exceed 100%. Although it is also necessary to analyse the percent coverage of the bottom quality to determine the habitat type, the coverage must **always equal** 100%.

Video interpretation begins by looking through the entire video once, after which the actual analysis commences. If the video quality is good, the beginning of the video, i.e. when the camera has reached the bottom, is interpreted from at least 30 seconds of moving image. If the habitat has not significantly changed during this period, only a single interpretation is carried out. Such a situation may arise, e.g. in a video where the first 45 seconds is a sand bottom with typical associated vegetation, after which the bottom quality changes to bedrock. In this case, the actual analysis is based on the sandy habitat in the first 30 seconds.

If the habitat clearly changes within the first 30 seconds, the interpretation is made on a habitat basis. In this case, one video will give two interpretations. However, a separately assessed habitat must appear in the video continuously for at least ten seconds and the area must be a clear and uniform. If the habitat changes more than twice during the video clip, those changes are unclear (e.g. from rock to sand), or the other habitat does not appear on the video for more than 30 seconds, an analysis is only carried out for a mixed substrate habitat.

In the video, the running time is recorded at the start and end of the analysis, and at the beginning and end of those parts interpreted as different habits. This makes it easy to return to the analysis afterwards. If two videos are interpreted from the video and the total duration is at most one minute, then the initial coordinates of the point are assigned to the first interpreted habitat and the end coordinates to the latter. However, interpretations should always be made on a case by case basis so that they best describe the underwater nature of the area filmed. The aforementioned 30-second guideline is only indicative and the interpreter should use their own professionalism and discretion.

Assessing the bottom quality and vegetation coverage can be challenging if the video has several different bottom types and abundant vegetation. The screen can then be thought of as a rectangle, such that a plant with 50% coverage should be visible on half of the screen for the entire interpretation period. In addition, video time can be used for analysis if the camera is moving at a steady speed. For example, a plant with a coverage of 25% should cover the entire screen (i.e. 100%) for a period of 7.5 seconds in a 30 second video. Although ROV videos are interpreted similarly to drop videos, the entire video is interpreted based on habitats and, if necessary, depths, without time limits.

Species identification from video

The identification of algae and vascular plants using video footage is very challenging and in most cases impossible, since many species can only be identified by microscope. In practice, only some large or exceptional species can be identified to species level from video, e.g. forkweed, *Furcellaria lumbricalis*, in its primary area of occurrence, as well as perfoliate pondweed, *Potamogeton perfoliatus*. The identification of plant species should not be based on data from the growth site or from the assessment of species found in similar habitats by other methods, such as diving. If the analyses are mainly based on experience-based information, the risk of systematic error is high. Specifically, one should be very careful when identifying filamentous algae, as the within-species variation is high and a definite species level identification often requires microscopic examination. For example, in most cases it is impossible to identify sea felt, i.e. *Pylaiella littoralis* or siphon weed species, i.e. *Polysiphonia* sp. to species level from video footage. Instead, the interpretation should use descriptive meta-levels, e.g. "filamentous brown" or "filamentous red". For annual algae, the colours are usually faded and therefore, for video interpretation purposes, many filamentous species have to be placed in the category of "unidentified filamentous". It is also worth remembering that video inventories are aimed at mapping habitats and their prevalence and thus, the identification of filamentous algae to species level is often unnecessary.

The species composition and identifiability from video footage varies greatly between sea areas. For example, in the species composition of the Gulf of Bothnia, it is possible to identify some plants to species level from video, whereas in other sea areas they would be easily confused with similar looking species. While some species can be easily identified from video in their main areas of prevalence, correct identification at the edges of their distribution may be impossible, e.g. due to small size, so that the species is not obvious from the video footage. Therefore, an interpreter of the video material needs to familiarise themselves with the sea area under research and to learn the levels to which different species groups and individual species can be identified from video. In addition, the downstream user of the material must understand the backgrounds of the data collected using the video method. For example, pondweed species form a meta-level group entitled *Potamogeton*

pectinatus/Potamogeton filiformis/Ruppia sp./*Zannichellia* sp., which may contain a completely different species composition depending on the marine area.

The video method is poorly suited to mapping the presence of fish and many benthic animals. Therefore, specifically designed mapping methods should be used to monitor them instead. Fish identifications to genus level are not useful for downstream data users and unnecessarily burdens information systems and thus, it is only worthwhile to record those observations that can be identified to species.

Presence data. Since the video image is in constant motion and it is impossible to control the camera's movement, some species or species group may only appear in the video momentarily. Often the camera focuses on a single algae or plant individual for only a very short time, or for example, when filamentous algae living under the larger bladder wrack are only visible if wave action moves the latter briefly aside. In such situations, although it is impossible to determine the total coverage of the species/species group in the interpretation area, the species can be safely said to be present in the video. In this case, presence information can be used that completely lacks a coverage estimate. The value for presence data is set to 0.001. The smallest possible percentage coverage is 0.1% for all species.

Faunal observations from videos

The coverage of sedentary or sessile animals, e.g. bivalves, barnacles, bryozoans, sponges and polyps, is estimated either as percent coverage or as numbers of individuals. The abundance estimation method used is presented in Chapter 6. With individuals or a very small number of specimens, a percentage tolerance of 0.1% is used, which is the lowest percent coverage available. It is also possible to make presence observations of fauna using the same principle as with plants and algae. When evaluating sedentary animals, it should be remembered that white-coloured species, e.g. bryozoans and bivalve shells reflect light well and thus, clearly stand out. This can easily increase their coverage estimate.

Fish species that are on priority list, including other mobile animals are recorded as individual numbers. If it is difficult or impossible to calculate the individual quantities, the most accurate estimate of the number of individuals is recorded.

Bottom quality

Video footage can only be used to form an interpretation of the surface layer of the seabed, based solely on what is seen in the video image. For example, a gravel surface which completely covers a clay stratum underneath is interpreted as a gravel bottom, despite the fact that the dominant sediment type is clay with only a thin layer of gravel on its surface. Thus, video interpretation differs substantially from geological mapping, which also maps the deeper layers of the sea floor.

Determining the quality of soft bottoms can be challenging. When filming, it is good to record preliminary observations about the bottom quality in the field protocol: for example, when the camera touches the bottom, the camera operator may feel whether the seafloor is hard

or soft. Although such observations can be utilised by the interpreter when performing the video analysis, they are not recorded in the LajiGIS database.

Further, silt, mud and clay can sometimes be distinguished from each other when the camera touches the bottom:

- Silt clouds up somewhat and when the camera is raised, the silt cloud is powdery and yellowish. Nevertheless, the camera does not usually sink deeply into the sediment, i.e. the video does not become completely black. Occasionally, holes and pits made by fish or burrowing benthic fauna are visible on the surface. A silt bottom also feels hard when the camera touches it.

- Mud bottoms are easily disturbed, forming a thick fine cloud and when the camera is raised from the bottom, small loose pieces of sediment may be visible. The camera unit often sinks completely into the sediment blocking the lens and the video is blacked out. The mud surface often displays bumps and depressions giving it a "cellulite-like" appearance.

- Clay is often difficult or impossible to recognise from a video. Although a clay surface resembles silt in the video, it does not cloud up like silt. Hard glacial clay may form strange lava-, concrete-shaped and/or sharp-edged ridges and formations on the bottom.

It is also sometimes challenging to determine the grain size of stones. When making an coverage estimate, it is good to remember the importance of bottom quality, i.e. what kind of environment is formed by this bottom type. Therefore, the most important thing is to separate those mobile grain sizes, e.g. sand and gravel, from stable bottom types, such as rock. The bottom may also be completely covered with vegetation, whereby the most important thing is to define the bottom quality as either mobile or non-mobile. The reliability of the ground quality estimate is also logged. The bottom quality categories are estimated using Velmu's grain size classes (Table 2).

The amount of loose sediment

The amount of loose sediment in analysed videos is estimated on a scale from 1 to 3.

0 = no sediment

1 = a little (when the camera touches the seabed, a small cloud of loose sediment is visible. It does not cover plants although small amounts may be detected, particularly on horizontal surfaces of the seafloor).

2 = moderate (sediment is visible on horizontal surfaces and the bottom is easily disturbed. There is also sediment on the surface of aquatic plants).

3 = abundant (loose sediment is plentiful and clearly covers all surfaces).

Occasionally, it is difficult to determine from video footage whether there is abundant sediment on the bottom or, if for example, silt or mud occurs among harder sediments such as gravel. In such cases, the presence of the tracks and/or faeces of benthic faunal species on soft bottoms should be examined from the footage. Based on such evidence, the bottom quality may be determined as soft. The amount of loose sediment does not need to be logged from soft bottom habitats, i.e. silt, mud or clay.

Other items for assessment

Video quality (i.e. video resolution and interpretability) is assessed on a scale from 1 to 3.

- 0 = Not assessed
- 1 = poor
- 2 = average
- 3 = good

Using other data collected at video points in video analysis

Video analysis can be supported by rake and benthic samples also taken at the video mapping point. The bottom quality data obtained with a bottom grab or a Luther-rake can be transferred directly to a video interpretation if the sample is taken from that video point. In addition, the species obtained with such samplers can be incorporated into the video analysis and labelled as presence information (0.001). If such extra sampling methods are utilised in the video interpretation, they must always be logged along with the video mapping method.

Saving the results of the video analysis

The LajiGIS marine protocol is used to record the video analysis results. Please note that recording video identification (video-ID) consistently is essential to integrate the material and original videos when needed.

Time use

The time required for drop video filming depends on the layout of the inventory points used. With regular grid points, video shooting from a boat requires approximately 5 to 20 minutes per sample point. This estimated time includes moving from one point to another, and the time range is due to their location (rocky shore *versus* open water), and the depth at each video point. Although shooting random video points also takes time, the boat driving time from one point to another may vary from a few minutes to an hour.

The time required for video analysis is directly related to the bottom quality, biodiversity and the number of discrete habits visible in the video footage. During a working day (8 hours), one person can reliably analyse approximately 30 to 80 videos. Transferring data from interpretation protocols to a table or database is slow and sufficient time should be reserved for this task: at least one day must be reserved for four days of data analysis.

Vegetation sampling by rake on soft bottoms and using such observations in video analysis

It is recommended to take samples from soft bottoms in order to support the video analysis. The vegetation samples collected by Luther-rake (Fig. 6) can be used to support the interpretation of the video footage. This method is particularly suitable for making accurate

species observations from the video point, whereby the amount of raked vegetation can be estimated from the video. In addition, raking may be used if video recording or diving does not result in the collection of material due to turbidity or if drifting plant material limits the assessment of the bottom quality, e.g. the bottom may be covered by extensive filamentous algal mats. The rake is thrown at least 5 to 10 times at the mapping point and continues until no new species are found. The vegetation is identified in the boat or at the laboratory. The information generated by raking is descriptive and is usually recorded as presence data (0.001) unless a video from the same point is recorded, whereby the raking results are stored in the video analysis in association with percent coverages. In this case, the mapping method is recorded as "video + rake (44)".

Fig. 6. A rake can be used to make observations of the bottom biota. This method is particularly suitable for verifying species observations made at video points and for areas where visual observation is not possible. However, raking does not give a quantitative description of species abundance or bottom quality. ©Metsähallitus / Essi Keskinen 2010

10. Benthic faunal sampling

Benthic faunal sampling from the soft seafloor

The purpose of sampling is to collect either quantitative or qualitative material that gives an overview of the biota. Samples are taken from a boat or a research vessel using a grab suspended on a wire cable. In this sampling context, 'shallow bottoms' means depths of less than 20 m, while 'deep bottoms' are depths greater than 20 m.

During the Velmu programme, benthic sampling has been carried out in summer, usually from July to September. This differs, for example, from the HELCOM monitoring guideline, according to which, monitoring is carried out from May to June. The timing of the Velmu sampling is designed to avoid an excessive abundance of the juvenile phases of benthic species in the samples.

The methods of sampling soft bottom fauna are based on sampling the entire biota of a given seabed area, whereby the number of different species or biomass per surface area can be determined. The type and bite area of each grab sampler used is logged in the field protocol and this data is transferred to the HERTTA POHJE data information system in association with the benthic sample data. The bottom faunal sample is quantitative, i.e. when the grab sample is properly closed, the sample volume is known. If the volume is unknown or the grab sampler is clearly leaking on retrieval, the sample is instead qualitative. The depth of the sample is measured on site either by sonar or using a wire cable marked at metre intervals. The depth is marked in the field protocol and later transferred to the information system as background data for that sample.

Deploying a grab sampler

When lowered from the surface, the passage of water through the grab may be hindered, particularly in the case of grab samplers with a biting action, e.g. van Veen-, Ekman-, and Ponar grabs. This can result in the production of a downward pressure wave in front of the grab that can cause loose surface sediment and surface-dwelling fauna to be displaced laterally when the grab reaches the bottom. Therefore, when deploying the sampler, its descent should be slowed sufficiently in time, i.e. from two to ten meters above the bottom, depending on the depth and conditions, after which the grab should be lowered to the seabed as slowly as possible. On touchdown, the grab is given a metre of slack on the cable/rope so that it sits evenly on the bottom. After this, the grab is triggered and lifted off the bottom with a smooth pull.

Sediment description and the determination of bottom quality

When the sediment sample is brought to the surface it is transferred to a tub or bucket and immediately photographed with a sign which includes information for that sampling site. If a sample is taken with a transparent plexiglass core, it is photographed with a measuring stick and a site information label before being transferred to a tub. A description of the sediment is made from the first sample. If replicate samples are taken, the first sample is compared

to the subsequent replicates. If the quality of the sediment clearly changes as sampling progresses, the location of the vessel should first be checked and consideration given to whether it is appropriate to move location. However, if the ship's position has remained unchanged, a description of the sediment is also made from the other samples.

A visual description of the sediment is based on the grain size of the sample, as well as the colour and odor of the sediment. The grain size determination is based on the bottom quality classification in Table 1 (which differs from the HERTTA classification). The total coverage of the bottom quality classes should always sum to exactly 100%.

In order to examine the bottom quality more closely, a separate sediment sample should be taken, if possible, with a core or an Ekman- or van Veen grab. The sampler is opened from above, the water above the sediment is drained and at least 50 cm³ of sediment is taken from the top three centimetres of the sample. The sample is clearly labelled, frozen and transported to the laboratory for further analysis, such as the determination of organic matter content. If necessary, the sample can also be stored in ethanol.

Benthic samplers for the soft seafloor

Van Veen. A van Veen sampler is a large, reliable grab that takes a sample of about 0.1 m² surface area from both soft, as well as sandy and fine gravel bottoms. If the van Veen is lowered to the bottom too quickly, the pressure wave built up in front of the sampler will displace the surface sediment. Therefore, its rate of descent, i.e. approximately 0.1–0.2 m², is slowed at about 10 m above the bottom. Due to its weight, a large van Veen can only be used with a winch from a large boat or ship. After bottom contact, the wire rope is allowed to slacken so that the vessel's movement does not jerk the grab, thereby also ensuring that the grab is allowed to sink deep enough into the sediment. The grab is then lifted to the surface at a steady speed. Benthic faunal samples cannot be taken when there are large waves, due to the lack of control while lowering the grab, leading to a decrease in sample quantitiveness. In practice, the wind limit depends on the size of the sampling vessel.

Van Veen sediment samples are deemed to be quantitative if their volume exceeds five litres (HELCOM Annex C-8 Soft bottom macrozoobenthos). Since benthic fauna mainly live in the sediment at depths ranging from 0–15 cm, a sample of more than five litres is considered sufficient to assess their abundance. In order to estimate the sediment volume, a scale can be marked on the tub to which the sediment sample is transferred. If the volume of the sample taken is less than five litres, sampling is repeated. The volume of the sample is then compared to the maximum volume of the grab sampler and the sample size logged.

If a quantitative sample is not achieved from a test site after two to three attempts, a qualitative sample can also be collected, e.g. if the sample has partially leaked between the jaws of the grab. The quantitative level of the sample is recorded with the code "E" or "not quantitative". In this case, samples of the fauna are not counted. Instead only the species are logged and the species list can be recorded in LajiGIS. If the qualitative criteria are not met, the species observations are recorded in the Microsoft® Excel file for modelling but are not transferred to the LajiGIS / HERTTA information systems.

Ekman- and Ponar grabs and Box core samplers. These samplers have a noticeably smaller bite area (about 0.2 m²) than a van Veen grab and in particular, both Ponar and Ekman samplers are suitable for smaller vessels because they do not require a winch (Fig. 3). However, a typical Box corer is heavier and requires a winch. Both Box corer and Ponar samples are triggered on the bottom when the cable is slackened (as with the van Veen) and are reliable. The Ekman grab is the easiest to lift and is triggered by rope messenger. Due to its lightness and its trigger mechanism, the Ekman grab is particularly sensitive to ship drift during sampling and is only suitable for shallow bottoms (<15 m). Species with very low densities are less well represented in samples taken with small grabs, i.e. smaller sampling area, compared with the larger samples taken by the van Veen grab. Depending on the purpose of the sampling, multiple replicates may be taken from one place, if necessary. However, the number of replicates required per sampler used will depend on the density of the biota and their distribution type.

Kuva 7. Benthic faunal sampling of the soft seafloor can be done with a Box corer (left) © SYKE 2009 or a Ponar-grab (right) © Metsähallitus/Juho Lappalainen 2014 (above) & Heidi Arponen 2013.

Sieving benthic faunal samples

In Velmu, benthic faunal samples are typically sieved using 0.5 mm and 1 mm mesh sieves (Fig. 4). In addition, a 5 mm sieve can also be used, if necessary, to separate out the larger sediment grain sizes and organisms. The sieving process is started by carefully pouring the water from the sample onto a stacked set of nested sieves with the finest (0.5 mm) mesh screen at the bottom. The sample is then transferred from the grab sampler to a sufficiently large vat or tub and the volume of the sediment sample is either evaluated visually or by using a measuring scale. This sample volume is then logged in the field protocol.

Fig. 2. Benthic fauna samples are sieved using 0.5 and 1.0 mm sieves in a stacked series (1.0 mm uppermost, 0.5 mm below) © Metsähallitus/Juho Lappalainen 2013 (left). © Metsähallitus/Kevin O'Brien 2013 (right).

Sieving continues by adding water to the sediment sample and gently blending the water-sediment mixture with a scoop or by hand. This mixture is poured in a series of small amounts onto a series of stacked sieves and the sediment is gently rinsed with a water hose through the screens until the entire sediment sample has been processed. Finally, the material retained on each sieve is gently rinsed with water into the corner. The material is then flushed into a sample jar using ethanol in a spray bottle. Materials left on the 1 mm and 0.5 mm screen are stored separately in their own jars. Alternatively, the sample can instead be sieved solely through a 0.5 mm mesh sieve into a sample jar, whereby separate 1 mm and 0.5 mm screening is performed later in the laboratory, prior to analysis.

Sieving should be carried out quickly but gently, especially for fragile animals, such as polychaete and oligochaete worms, which are easily damaged when flushed through the screen series. Nevertheless, the sieving process should be done carefully enough that the material remaining on the screen represents the mesh size of the screen used and no extra finer material remains. If the sediment passes easily through the sieves, larger animals remaining on the screens can be picked directly with forceps and placed into sample jars. This can mainly be done with 1 mm mesh sieves. If the sample contains stiff glacial clay which does not contain benthic animals, the clay lumps can be left without pouring onto the sieve and their surfaces rinsed into the sample using a syringe. In practice, clay lumps should only be removed at the point when no more animals are found in that fraction of the material remaining to be sieved. Larger stones are processed in a similar fashion. The sieving of sand samples and the separation of benthic organisms is described in the section on benthic faunal sampling of sand and gravel.

The organic material can be rinsed along with the benthic fauna into the same jar. If some of the animals are picked out, the remaining bottom material can be stored in its own jar. In this case, it is logged in the field protocol that the sample comprises two jars, which also contain the labels as follows:

- The first jar contains approximately half of the sample = 1a
- The second jar contains the remainder of the sample = 1b

The same approach is applied if more sample jars are required due to the high amount of bottom material. If no animals are found in the sample, such information should also be recorded in the field protocol.

Sample labelling and preservation

Sieved material remaining on 0.5 mm and 1 mm mesh screens and any duplicate samples are always stored and handled separately. Site information should be written in pencil on both the side of the sample jar as well as on a paper label stored inside. Such information should include: the station code and depth, the date of sampling, sieve mesh size, duplicate sample number (e.g. 1/3) and a possible letter code (a, b, etc.). Thus, if there is more than one jar from the same sample, they can be labelled 1/3 a, 1/3 b, and so on.

Samples are stored in 70% ethanol (final concentration). If the sample contains a lot of water retaining material such as sand, organic matter or algae, pure ethanol can be poured into the sample jar so that the proportion of ethanol is at least two thirds of the total sample. Once closed, the sample jars are gently rotated to spread the ethanol throughout the sample and to aid in its preservation. The volume of ethanol should exceed the sample material to ensure the whole sample remains below the liquid surface.

The samples are ideally stored in a cool, dark place until they are ready for analysis. Storage is best carried out using glass or plastic containers which have sealable lids. Such containers should be designed for, or have been shown to be effective in preserving benthic samples. The samples should be checked from time to time to ensure that the lids are still sealed and that the ethanol has not evaporated away.

Environmental variable data in association with sampling

If basic information on environmental variables such as water temperature, salinity and oxygen content is required, a water sample is also taken from the benthic fauna sampling point. A water sample is taken from one metre above the bottom, using a Limnos sampler or from the water surface using a core sampler if a Limnos is not available. The collected data is logged in databases as environmental variables which describe the sample. The data will be utilised in modelling the occurrence of underwater habitats and species.

Benthic faunal sampling of sand and gravel

Under the Velmu programme, benthic fauna are sampled on sand and gravel bottoms using cores or a Tvärminne sampler. A core sampler is usually a plastic or plexiglass tube of at least 20 cm in height, and 8 cm in diameter. The surface area of the sampler used is always recorded. The core is pushed into the bottom to a depth of at least 10 cm. When the core is

in the bottom, a rubber bung seals the top, after which it is transferred to a glass jar. The bung is only removed when the bottom of the core is inside the glass jar. The core is then slowly lifted and its contents transferred to the jar. Finally, a lid is added to the glass jar. In this way, dozens of core samples can be taken during a single dive. Alternatively, several cores may be used, which are closed with a second bung at the lower end and the samples are only transferred to jars on the surface. In order to obtain a representative sample, many replicates must be taken on sandy bottoms and when using narrow diameter cores.

Due to their low organic content, samples taken from the sandy seabed do not require separate sieving in the field. The water in the jar is replaced with ethanol and, if desired, rose bengal dye is added to stain all organic material pink. The sample jar is inverted so that the ethanol is evenly mixed throughout the whole sample. Sand samples contain a lot of water, so it is recommended to use undiluted ethanol to achieve a final concentration of about 70% alcohol. Extracting the animals from the sand is done in the laboratory prior to analysis: the sand sample is poured in small quantities into a larger bucket with plenty of water, mixed thoroughly and the animals that come to the surface are poured onto the sieve. The remaining ethanol is rinsed into a sample jar. Here, mixing means imparting a sufficiently rapid rotation that both the animals and sand move with the water. Subsequently, the material that has risen to the surface is quickly poured onto a sieve. Rinsing should continue until the animals no longer appear on the surface of the water-sand mixture. The remaining sand should also be examined in order to find other heavier organisms, such as small gastropods, bivalve molluscs and crustaceans.

Benthic sampling of hard bottoms

The purpose of sampling hard bottoms is to collect quantitative data or material that gives an overview of the biota present. Since the use of many types of boat-deployed grabs is difficult or impossible on hard bottoms, sample material is usually collected by diving. In this methodology guide, diving sampling is recommended only from shallow, hard bottoms. Nevertheless, an appropriately trained professional diver can also take such samples from considerably deeper.

Determining the sampling point on shallow hard bottoms

The quantitative sampling method for the hard seabed is based on sampling the entire biota of a known selected surface area, whereby the species composition, the number of individual organisms, and where appropriate, species biomass can be determined per unit area.

Samples collected from each sampling site are taken from the main zones of an area, which are optimal in terms of faunal communities and their biomass. As such, in the western Gulf of Finland and in the Archipelago Sea, samples should generally represent discrete belts of filamentous algae, bladder wrack and red algae/blue mussel zones. In the eastern Gulf of Finland, these zones change to filamentous algae, bladder wrack and green filamentous algae. In more northern areas, the various zones contain those communities that best maintain that area's biodiversity. From each dive line, one sample is obtained from the optimum depths and habitats of the biota in the area. Therefore, three samples are taken for each dive line. Sampling depths are selected from 0 to 2, 2 to 4, and 4 to 6 metre depth

zones representing the different communities. Where possible, samples are taken next to the vegetation line but if the target habitat or suitable sampling substrate is not present on the dive line, the sample can also be taken from farther away. In this case, the habitat is logged. The bottom gradient is also evaluated for each sample.

Sampling with a Kautsky square

The Kautsky square is used for mapping the benthos living on hard bottoms. It has a sample area of 20 x 20 cm and is composed of a frame and a collection bag. If the bottom is composed of relatively small stones, a smaller, 15 x 15 cm Kautsky can be used instead. The size of the frame used should be logged on the field protocol. The bag should be made from a durable fabric with a mesh size of no more than 0.3 mm. It is highly recommended to use individual collection bags, so that samples taken from different depths can easily be kept separate. The sample contains those living organisms in the frame area that are scraped off the rock into the collection bag using a spatula. Before sampling, the diver rests firmly on the seabed and places the frame on flat bedrock or a stone so that the frame is firmly against the bottom. If the surface has a steep gradient, the sample must be collected while the diver is above the bottom (Fig. 9). It is recommended that the diver must then be slightly negatively buoyant in order to hold position. Although the diver can also take samples from vertical surfaces, this requires perfect buoyancy control so that the frame does not move during sampling. Taking a Kautsky sample in open water is not recommended for Velmu surveys because of the technical challenge, and because biota on vertical walls differs from that found on horizontal surfaces. Before scraping the sample from the bottom, the diver checks that there are no gaps between the frame and the rock. The surface gradient is estimated in degrees (0 to 90 degrees; where 0° is horizontal and 90° is vertical).

During sampling, the sample material is scraped using a spatula with the mouth of the frame towards the diver, so that the collection bag runs between the legs. The sample is scraped into the bag only after ensuring that no leakage occurs between the bottom and the frame, and that the diver's position is fixed in place. The area inside the frame is scraped thoroughly and the frame should not move at this time. When the area is clean, the sample is transferred to the bottom of the bag and tied off above the sample. At this point, the diver should ensure that all animals go to the bottom of the bag and are not added to the next sample by accident. If macroscopic vegetation, aquatic plants, or macrolides lie within the test frame, they are collected as a part of the sample and are identified later in the laboratory.

Only successful samples should be retained. If the diver notices that some of the sample has escaped, he can turn the bag inside out underwater, empty it and take a new sample. Finally, it is worth mentioning that sampling with a Kautsky square will not succeed if the bedrock or rock surface is very uneven. Therefore, sampling can only be done on smooth bedrock or stone surfaces.

Kautsky samples can be loosely placed in labelled bags in water-filled buckets and can be transferred to sample jars at the end of the field day. Sample transfer, sieving, and other processing is described in the following section, as is the labelling and preservation of sample material.

Fig. 9. Kautsky sampling on a steep gradient. A sediment sieve is a good way to separate the fauna of hard bottoms into different size classes. of hard solids into different sizes © Mats Westerborn.

Sampling from deep hard bottoms

It is difficult to collect quantitative samples from deep hard bottoms since ship-deployed grabs do not work and the depth limits a diver's working time, while increasing the risks. Although various rakes can collect different species, they are selective and random and so they are not recommended. Observations of the general characteristics of the biota can be collected with the help of underwater video cameras, particularly where those observations consist mainly of large species.

Processing and analysis of benthic faunal samples

Sieving and preservation of benthic fauna in the laboratory

Benthic animals are typically preserved in 70 % ethanol in airtight jars in a cool, dark place until they are ready to be analysed. It should be noted that when preserving samples, the final concentration of ethanol should be close to 70 %. If the sample contains water or water retaining sand, a stronger concentration should be used initially. The shelf life of samples should also be checked if they are to be stored for a long period. There are differences in the processing of soft- (taken with Ponar-, Ekman grabs, etc.) and hard bottom benthic faunal samples (Kautsky square).

- Soft bottom faunal samples are sieved on 0.5 and 1.0 mm sieves, if this has not already been done in the field. Samples may be sieved once again before analysis if they contain a lot of fine sediment, which makes them more difficult to examine. Sieving soft bottom benthic animal samples is explained in more detail in the above section "Sieving benthic faunal samples".
- The Kautsky samples (hard bottom) are screened according to an area's species and the characteristics of the sample, either through a series of sieves or with only 0.5 and 1.0 mm mesh screens. A tower of sieves of decreasing mesh sizes is recommended to determine the size distribution of animals, while separating algae and other matter from the fauna. In particular, the use of such a series of often speeds

up both the processing and identification of samples containing large amounts of blue mussels and algae.

The amount of residue (sand, degradable algae and plant material, etc.) is estimated on a scale of +, 1, 2, or 3 and written on the protocol. Only the most obvious residue material is recorded in the field protocol during sampling. This estimate can be supplemented in the laboratory when the sample is processed and examined under the microscope.

Fig. 3. Samples are preserved in sealable jars which contain sufficient ethanol (70 %). © Metsähallitus/Roosa Mikkola 2014.

Sieving Kautsky samples

Macrophytes and their associated invertebrate species, as well as the numbers of individuals are determined from the sample. If they are available, it is recommended to use a series of nested sieves. Such a series accelerates the analysis of the samples and increases analytical accuracy, particularly in samples containing a high biomass of organisms. Such abundant samples can be screened through 10 (9.5) mm, 4 mm, 2 mm, 1 mm and 0.5 mm sieves. However, if the animal biomass is very small and only consists of small individuals, screening with 1mm and 0.5 mm sieves may be sufficient. The biota of the sample is identified in the laboratory.

If a series of nested sieves is not used and there are a limited number of mussels (e.g. in the eastern Gulf of Finland and the Kvarken), the length of the molluscs is also measured. This is done using either a ruler or Vernier callipers to separate the age and size classes of species such as *Mytilus*, *Dreissena* and *Mytilopsis*. Alternatively, size classes can also be checked visually for the following size groups: 0.5 to 1, 1 to 2, 2 to 5, 5 to 10, and 10 to 15 mm, etc. These size classes correspond to the sizes classes of molluscs remaining on the 0.5, 1, 2, 4 and 10 mm mesh sieves, respectively. In samples with abundant mussels, length measurements can be done from the sample. **In 2022, the size classes of benthic animals in Velmu were not directly measured per se.**

While several methods can be employed to speed up the processing of samples with abundant algae, it is recommended to use a series of nested sieves. There are several ways

of separating algae and animals. However, the most important thing after rinsing the algae is to go through the sample under a microscope to detect small species. First, the sample containing the algae is poured over the nested sieve series and rinsed with plenty of water. For example, some proven methods involve rinsing the seaweed in abundant water and pouring the wash water back over the screen, or by 'combing' the algae with forceps in water and rinsing the thallus onto the sieve. If there is a lot of algae, it can be partitioned into smaller amounts after careful rinsing (see instructions for partitioning).

Extraction and counting of algae and fauna

Using a fine forceps, animals are picked from a sufficiently small amount of bottom material under a magnifying lamp and/or a stereoscopic microscope. Fauna that are scarce and also those which require more precise microscopy should be picked separately to their own Petri dish, while species which are abundant can be counted directly from the sample itself. The number of species, as well as the number of individuals per species are counted for each sample. Both whole animals and the heads of broken animals are counted as individuals. The other broken parts of individual animals are counted and the sum of the parts used to determine a minimum number.

When handling a sample, all animal species and their individual numbers, the size classes of the molluscs, as well as the sediment type and its quantity on a scale of 0 to 3 (mud, sand, etc.) should be logged separately for each screen size used. Kautsky samples also identify algal species and their abundance using similar scales. In order to speed up the work and that no information is forgotten, it is advisable to use a ready-made protocol that includes all of these information categories, including which species are typically found in the area.

A microscope is always used whenever material from a 0.5 mm sieve is handled. Sample material from a 1 mm mesh sieve can also be microscoped or if there are large animals, they can also be counted and determined easily by eye. If the samples are rich in inorganic material, they can be stained with rose bengal dye solution before counting.

The bottom fauna are separated from the algal mass. The cost of finding abundant numbers of individuals of a certain species must be weighed against the value of any additional information obtained. Using a microscope does not ensure accurate work if the sample is not first divided into sufficiently small portions such that all individuals can be detected. Therefore, overloading a Petri dish with sample material does not guarantee accurate results.

When identifying mussel species, it is advisable to also consider the possibility of alien species occurring in the sample, such as *Dreissena polymorpha*, *D. bugensis*, and *Mytilopsis leucophaeata*. If the initial identification is uncertain, some shells should be opened to check inside the umbone in order to find the distinguishing characteristics which aid in identifying the molluscs to species level, where possible.

Species occurrences recorded as presence/absence data

- Hydrozoa are recorded as presence/absence data when in colony form. *Hydra* polyps are marked as individuals.
- Barnacles, e.g. *Amphibalanus* are recorded as presence/absence data as crushed shells but as individuals when intact. Barnacles growing on the upper surfaces of blue mussels are calculated in the same way as the amount of blue mussels.
- Bryozoans, e.g. *Einhornia crustulenta*, are recorded as presence/absence data.
- Presence/absence can be marked in Microsoft® Excel lajiGIS as either 1 or 0. The number 1 is only marked for one fraction so that it cannot be read as >1.

Water fleas and plankton

Water fleas and plankton are not counted because specimens may easily become mixed with those derived from the seawater used for flushing that do not belong to the original sample. However, if we want to consider zooplankton species from different areas, e.g. the Eastern Gulf of Finland or Bothnian Bay, we must ensure that they are living benthic species, such as cyclopoids, e.g. the large-sized *Limnocalanus* sp. Animal plankton species or groups are generally marked as presence/absence data, since most individuals pass easily through a 0.5 mm sieve, and therefore reliable quantitative values are not obtained.

Sample partitioning

Sample partitioning should be avoided in most cases, because even if a sample divided by the correct partitioning method can be seen to represent common species, a species with a small number of individuals will be easier to miss, or their number will be over represented instead. For example, if a whole sample contains only two individuals of a particular species and the sample is divided into eight boxes on a sorting tray, of which two are examined, there is only a 25 % probability that this species will be detected. This problem is particularly acute when replicates are missing from the samples, i.e. each sample is the only one that represents that particular sampling area in question. Errors caused by partitioning are balanced out by using replicates. However, if partitioning is carried out, it must be done in a way that does not affect the final result and the sample used must be representative of the the whole population. For example, the grid on the sorting tray does not represent a completely neutral partitioning method, because more or less material is easily left at the edges and corners of the tray than in other sections.

Nevertheless, partitioning and partial sample analysis may be justified when the sample is so large that the cost of its analysis is disproportionately expensive compared to the additional information gained. This is also something that needs to be decided at a local level based on experience and circumstances. If it has been found and clarified that partitioning does not affect the reliability of the final result, and if the whole sample analysis is disproportionately expensive, then partitioning is justified. If necessary, the sample can be processed differently, e.g. the most abundant species are counted from the partitioned sample. From the remaining unselected sample, a low number of sufficiently small batches should still also be examined under the microscope to find sparse species, so that these can also be noticed among the most abundant species.

In samples containing large aquatic plants, partitioning can be carried out based on the wet weight of the sample. Finally, the end result is multiplied by a factor according to the partitioning employed. A reference to the partition used should be entered into the data

system for the sample's metadata, for which the HERTTA information system has its own sampling data heading.

Species identification

Species identification should be carried out by experienced personnel, preferably those who have undergone a proficiency test in taxonomy. Alternatively, inexperienced people should have the possibility of being advised by a more experienced taxonomist to verify the accuracy of the species identification. Each laboratory should also have its own comparative species collection, with which inexperienced people can confirm unclear species identifications by comparing their specimens to the reference collection material.

Benthic macrofauna are mainly identified to species level whenever possible. The identification is done to the genus level if the individuals are very small and the species identification traits are not yet fully developed (e.g. small *Gammarus* or *Idotea* species). In practice, *Gammarus* specimens retained on a 0.5 mm mesh sieve are not identified to species level due to undeveloped species characteristics. Instead, they are recorded as *Gammarus* sp. or *Gammarus* sp. juveniles. Species identification is only recommended for specimens greater than 5 mm and only then if the identifier has sufficient taxonomic knowledge. Moreover, due to the difficulty of identification, some of the larger *Gammarus* specimens, especially females, must be left as a species pair, e.g. *G. salinus*/*G. zaddachi*).

If it is not possible to determine all individuals to species level within an effective time frame, a subsample of that species group may be taken and determined to species level instead. For example, hundreds of gammarid amphipods (*Gammarus*) may occur in one sample and identifying each individual to species level would not be cost effective. Therefore, a representative subsample should be taken and individuals identified to species level where possible. A representative sample should be both quantitative and qualitative, i.e. individuals selected for identification should be randomly selected, not based on size, so that not only the more easily identified larger individuals are selected.

The determination of oligochaete worms stops at the subclass level, while chironomid larvae are identified to family level. In addition, the determination of ostracod crustaceans (Ostracoda), water mites (Hydracarina) and polyps (Cnidaria) can be left to the upper taxonomic levels. Some worm-like or other soft-bodied species can only be determined to the upper levels, since not all of the species-specific identification characteristics can be recognised from preserved specimens, e.g. ribbon worms (Nemertea) and flatworms (Turbellaria).

It is advisable for all personnel carrying out species identification to learn both new and older alien species at regular intervals to keep their skills up to date. New benthic- and alien faunal species have also been found in the Velmu benthic material.

In the inner archipelago, shallow coastal bays and river estuaries, the proportion of oligochaete worms and various insects, particularly chironomid larvae, can be significant within a community. Although it is advisable to identify these fauna to species level in such areas, this often requires the input of a specialist when identifying these groups. Therefore, such species should be picked from a sample to a separate jar and if possible, forwarded to an expert for identification.

Counting and identifying snails and bivalves

Empty shells are not included in individual number counts. Nevertheless, both empty snail and bivalve shells, in particular blue mussel shells, should be checked as other benthic organisms are often hidden inside. The number of *Hydrobia* snails in large samples is easily overestimated, since dead individuals are difficult to distinguish from living specimens. To avoid this, in an abundant sample, approximately twenty specimens can be randomly selected and their shells broken to examine which are empty and which contain tissue. If snails are examined under a lighted microscope, it is generally easy to see whether the animal is inside or not. The genus *Hydrobia* is difficult to identify to species level, thus in most cases it is sensible to leave the determination at the genus level, particularly in preserved samples. Similarly, unless species identification is very clear and easy, it is also often advisable to identify freshwater gastropod snails to the genus level only.

If species identification is unsuccessful for a particular species or group of species, fresh or preserved samples should be sent for identification to the Finnish Museum of Natural History. This institute does not deal with extensive plant or benthic faunal material but is solely responsible for specific issues related to species identification.

Length measurements of benthic fauna

In 2022, the size classes of benthic animals in Velmu were not directly measured *per se*. Instead, the systematic use of a series of nested sieves is required in the Velmu benthic inventories because it gives a broad overview of the size classes of organisms. In addition, the absence of a particular species on a sieve indicates that it has not yet reached a certain size at that particular sampling site.

The determination of the size classes of benthic fauna is justified when more detailed information is needed on the structure, dynamics and functioning of the benthic community. The size of invertebrates affects their functionality and also informs about the status of the benthic community. The Marine Strategy Directive of the European Union guideline directs habitat monitoring based on the size distribution of benthic populations, as well as other factors which describe the state of the benthic community.

The measurement guide comes from the quality assurance manual directive, i.e. '3701 Determination of benthic species, number and biomass', of the Finnish Environment Institute's Maritime Centre, which provides detailed instructions for taking the length measurements of different species. If there is no separate measurement guideline for a particular species, the length is determined as the total length of the individual. In abundant samples of bivalves, polychaete worms and crustaceans, a minimum of at least 100 individuals are measured for each sample. Samples with large numbers of specimens can be partitioned, for example, with an Elmgren splitter (Elmgren 1973). Small organisms are measured using the ocular micrometer in the microscope, while the lengths of bivalves or other fauna greater than 5 mm are taken with callipers. Measurement is always carried out at the same magnification, e.g. by using a 10 x ocular lens, with a 6 x objective lens.

- **Bivalves (Mollusca).** The length (width) of bivalve molluscs is measured to distinguish between age and size classes.
- **Polychaete worms (Polychaeta).** Both *Marenzelleria*- ja *Hediste*- (*Nereis*) species are measured at their widest segments (usually from the fifth to tenth). The chaetae (bristles) are also included in the measurements. This method is used because the worms stretch and break apart easily during preprocessing, which makes it difficult to get accurate full length measurements afterwards. The scaleworm, *Bylgides sarsi* is measured from the first pair of eyes to the posterior spine. Many polychaete worms are measured for their total length when they are preserved intact and when the eyes cannot be distinguished in preserved specimens.
- **Isopods (Crustacea).** Size classes of large benthic isopods such as *Saduria entomon* and other marine isopod species, e.g. *Idotea*, *Jaera*, etc., are determined by measuring from between the eyes to the tip of the telson. Large benthic isopods are placed onto absorbent paper, their bodies straightened carefully and then measured using callipers. Specimens less than 5 mm and other smaller marine isopod species are measured under the microscope, using a micrometer eyepiece.
- **Amphipods (Crustacea).** Amphipod species such as *Monoporeia*, *Pontoporeia*, *Gammarus*, etc., are measured from the bases of the antenna to the tip of the telson. Specimens are kept completely submerged in water in a Petri dish and carefully straightened using a fine forceps and a preparation needle before measurement. Based on their measurements, the amphipod *Monoporeia affinis* is further separated into size classes of 1 mm increments for subsequent weight measurements.

Recording benthic faunal identification data

The results are recorded in the POHJE benthic fauna register of the HERTTA environmental data management system. Recording instructions can be found in the system. If help is needed in storing data, contact Jouko Rissanen (jouko.rissanen@ymparisto.fi) of the SYKE Maritime Centre.

Preservation of samples after identification

Samples are preserved in 70 % ethanol after identification. Small specimens are retained completely. In samples with abundant mussels, large specimens remaining on the largest mesh sieves, i.e. 4 mm and 9 mm, can be disposed of after sample treatment to save space. Rare and interesting species are placed separately in small Eppendorf tubes or similar containers within the same jar along with the rest of the sample. Unidentified animals and algae should always be preserved.

Representative samples of all species are saved to a reference collection. Samples are stored in Eppendorf tubes, which should also include information about the location, date and depth of sampling

11. Orientation for inventory mapping

Velmu mapping surveys require a very wide range of expertise. Surveyors must know how to navigate the sea areas, use the equipment and the sampling gear, be familiar with both the species and special features of the area, and when making dive surveys, should also be a professional diver.

In order to ensure the quality of the material to be collected, familiarisation with the mapping work is very important. The surveyor must comprehensively know both the methods used, as well as the biological species of an area. In addition, it is important to manage the storage of the collected field data collected within a nationally consistent format. This is particularly important, since vague or incorrectly recorded observations make it difficult to edit and use the data.

Before beginning the survey, each person involved in the mapping work must be taught or must revise at least:

- i. Methods according to the latest methodological guidelines
- ii. The species of the area, in particular the attributes of the Velmu priority species
- iii. Correct recording of the data
- iv. Occupational safety guidelines

Mapping tasks while diving

One of the most important factors limiting the use of diving results in dive surveys is the subjectivity of the evaluation of species and number of organisms. Divers should therefore practice evaluating vegetation coverage at the beginning of the survey period and also occasionally, either with other divers or with the help of test plots of known surface area. It is also recommended that divers should undergo a coverage perception test in association with that described for videoanalysis. Inadequate knowledge of the species can also affect the usability of the material. Participants in underwater mapping work should therefore have an appropriate education in the natural sciences, adequate diving training and diving experience, and knowledge of biological species in the inventory area. Attention should also be paid to staff orientation and revisional training. The diver must also have suitable diving equipment for work (Chapter 7). To ensure occupational safety, the diver must be trained and instructed in the equipment used and the dives must follow the appropriate dive safety guidelines.

Video filming

Before the first drop-video session, the video team must be trained regarding the quality requirements of the videos so that the end result is of sufficient quality and can be analysed. It is also good for the team to familiarise themselves with the video material filmed earlier, as well as the basics of videoanalysis before starting to film in the field. The most common problems with video analysis are caused by the camera consistently either being too far from or too close the bottom, or that the camera is moving too fast. The first videos filmed

by new personnel should always be reviewed with experienced analysts and the quality of the videos discussed.

Video analysis

The personnel who are analysing videos should be carefully trained for the task. The ability to identify the species of a given area should be well established before the analysis begins and it is always good to practice identifying the species or groups of species in the video with an experienced interpreter. It is advisable to start with the interpretation of areas or mapping points which have low biodiversity and gradually move on to more complex bottom types. Moreover, it is also recommended that people with previous experience in analysing videos should review the standards each year before starting video interpretation, including sufficiently often during the analysis period.

When interpreting videos, it should be remembered that this is purely a descriptive method. The analyst can never analyse a video completely correctly or incorrectly, the evaluation is always subjective and may even vary by the same person at different times. The interpreter should not use too much time to get the correct percent coverage values, as the absolute percent coverages are impossible to determine from the video image. Therefore, whether the video is watched two or twenty times, the coverage estimate is just as good. It is essential to remember that drop-video inventories are mainly aimed at mapping communities and habitats and not exact coverages at the species level. Thus, the most important factor is to get the magnitude of both the bottom quality and vegetation coverage percentages in the correct order, and to distinguish different habitats from each other, i.e. hard or soft bottom.

Joint Interpretation. Videos are interpreted at least once a year, usually in a group of three to four people. Each person writes their own percent coverage estimates for both bottom quality and biota, after which the estimates are compared between the interpreters. The difference in coverage between individuals should not exceed 10%. Based on their bottom type and biota, different types of videos should be interpreted together for a few hours to ensure consistency between individuals. Thereafter, and before any independent interpretation work, it is also advisable to perform a percentage perception test.

Model Videos. After the joint interpretation and percentage cover perception test, it is recommended to review so-called 'model' videos. In the future, some animated example videos which have been analysed using general standards will be made available for all inventory personnel: species and observations will be marked in the videos with arrows and circles along with explanations. Model videos will include:

- ✓ A simple deep habitat video (one habitat)
- ✓ A video with habitat changes (multiple habits within the same video)
- ✓ A filamentous algae video (observations cannot always be made at the species level!)
- ✓ A video from a shallow mixed bottom (a so-called 'difficult' video with multiple bottom types and abundant vegetation)
- ✓ A vascular plant video (tall and thin vegetation coverage)

Percent perception test for divers and video interpreters

Before diving surveys or interpreting videos, it is important to learn how to perceive percent coverages with areas of known coverage. The test is done using white and coloured sheets of A4-sized paper. Four white A4 sheets are compiled into an evaluation area. Thus, two A4 sheets make up 50% of the surface area, one comprises 25%, and so on. The test organiser tears up different coloured papers in predetermined surface area ratios and adds them to the estimation area. The participants in the test do not know these percentages and their task is to evaluate the percent coverage of the different coloured paper within the evaluation area. The concept is to give interpreters a picture of how the actual percent coverages appear. During the test, it is also worthwhile noting how the different colours and sizes of the pieces of paper affect their percent coverage evaluations.

12. Other Velmu field surveys

Side scan sonar

At its best, side scan sonar is able to produce high-resolution acoustic images or sonograms from the seabed. Compared to other sonar methods, side scanning does not measure depth but is based instead on the intensity of the returning echo signal. Although it is possible to map large areas quite rapidly and cost effectively using side scan sonar, this method often requires other underwater mapping methods to verify the interpretation of the material.

NB! Charting the seabed on with side scan sonar is a licensed activity! An exploration permit **MUST** be applied from The Finnish Military Forces well in advance of the planned survey period.

There is no dedicated guideline for side scan sonar surveying within Velmu. However, the methodology prepared by Metsähallitus can be utilised as appropriate (Appendix I).

Fig. 11. In the sonogram, the seabed appears to consist mainly of sand and partly of stones and gravel also. The adjacent drop-video image on the left verifies that in the area in the red box consists of sand. © Metsähallitus 2014.

Fig. 12. Based on the sonogram image, the seabed consists of a fine soft bottom material with patches of vegetation (red box). This is confirmed by the adjacent picture. © Metsähallitus.

Mapping fish reproduction areas

Under the Velmu programme, the Finnish Natural Resource Centre (LUKE) is responsible for mapping and modelling fish breeding areas. The aim of such surveys is to compile data on the location of the breeding areas of various fish species along the Finnish coast, as well as the temporal and local distribution of environmental factors affecting reproduction. The person responsible for questions related to surveys in LUKE is Antti Lappalainen. The various methods used in fish reproduction surveys are described in:

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Appendix I: Instruction manual for the side scan sonar unit (model DE680D) used in Metsähallitus

NB! Charting the seabed on with side scan sonar is a licensed activity! An exploration permit MUST be applied from The Finnish Military Forces well in advance of the planned survey period.

Hardware

The side scan sonar system used by Metsähallitus, i.e. model DE680D, is made by the Swedish company DeepVision Ab (Fig. 1). Further reading material on the use of the company's hardware and software can be accessed [here](#). The system consists of a side scan probe or "fish", the rear part of which contains the emitter. The hardware also includes a towing cable and drum reel for towing the fish, as well as an intermediate cable and a data processor. This is a two-way system, with data coming from the probe through the processor to a recording unit (a laptop computer), from which electric current feeds the data processor and probe. In addition, data is recorded, stored, processed and analysed using the side scan software programme DeepView 4.1 (Fig. 2), also produced by DeepVision Ab. The GPS and sonar hardware of a vessel form an integral part of the side scan sonar system. It is possible to combine information from the towing vessel's chart plotter with the side scan sonar system, whereby both the location and depth data are stored in real time within the side scan material itself.

Fig. 1. Side scan sonar system model DE680D and its component parts: 1. Probe or "fish"

2. Towing cable and drum 3. Intermediate cable 4. Data processor 5. Recording unit (laptop).

Fig. 2. A screenshot of the side scan sonar software programme DeepView 4.1. The upper panel shows the object window. The lower panel shows the map view with the vessel's location and depth, as well as its speed and bearing. The panel on the left is the Project Navigator window.

Setting up the side scan sonar system

Installation of the side scan software programme

Installing the side scan programme onto your computer is done by first installing the DeepVision and licensing files (see DeepVision for more information). The Navionics map base (Navionics Gold 44XG, Baltic Sea and inland waters) is then installed as follows. Download the electronic map material (usually in the form of a microSD card) to your computer. After this, ensure that the "Show hidden files and folders" feature on Windows is activated. When this function is activated, a text file called 'nTag' should appear in the map material folder. This file needs to be displayed so that the map material can be exported to the side scan programme. Next, open the side scan sonar programme and double-click the map window. In the "Map View Settings" window that opens, "Navionics" is selected as the "Map Server", and the "Chart Folder" determines from which folder the programme searches for map material. The folder path should look like this, e.g. C:\Users\DeepVision\Desktop\Navionic_charts\Navionic\Charts.

Assembly and testing

The assembly of the side scan sonar system is carried out as follows. Begin by connecting the towing cable to the "fish" as shown in Fig. 3. The cable is then connected to the USB port on the computer via the intermediate cable and data processor box. Note that although the terminals on both the cable reel and the intermediate cable do not have an actual locking mechanism, the connector is pushed in and should "click" into place. After combining the side scanning system, the boat's chart plotter should be connected to the recording unit (laptop). The Metsähallitus boats have a pre-installed cable from the plotter with a female RS232 serial terminal, which is connected to the USB port of the computer via a corresponding USB to RS232 male serial cable (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. The towing cable is connected to the probe as shown. To ensure that the fish swims horizontally, the safety towing rope is attached by shackle to the second hole from the back.

Fig. 4. A USB to RS232 serial cable. This is used to connect the boat's chart plotter to the side scan sonar recording unit (laptop) and side scan software programme. This allows real time recording of the vessel's location, speed and bearing, as well as the depth.

When all the different parts of the side scan system are connected, it can be turned on and the side scan programme initiated. It should be noted that if the laptop computer being used has a built-in GPS receiver, this may need to be deactivated before starting the programme. Once the side scan programme is started, ensure that it is connected to both the fish and the vessel's chart plotter. This is done by checking if both the echo and depth data recording buttons are red. If they are greyed out, they are not connected. In addition, check that the data from the plotter (coordinates, speed, direction and depth) are displayed and updated in the upper left corner of the map view window. To ensure that the probe is sending sonar data to the computer, press the blue, triangular "Play" button and the programme should start to display a real-time sonogram in the upper waterfall view window (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Sonogram toolbar from left to right: Record sonar data, show sonar live data, sonar setup, playback selected file, stretch side scan lines to fit width, show an overview of scan file, show non-stretched lines, measure distance, measure height, zoom.

The side scan programme normally links with the probe almost immediately and with the chart plotter after a few minutes. If the programme does not find the probe and/or the plotter, check that all the wires are connected properly and restart the computer. Also, ensure that the ship's data logger (black box), if installed on the vessel, is not connected to the plotter via the cable going to the probe. If it is, it is possible for the datalogger to block communication between the plotter and

the side scan programme. To resolve this issue, either turn off the datalogger or install a secondary cable between the plotter and the data logger.

Configuring side scan settings

Before beginning the actual side scanning process, the skew settings in the “Towfish setup” window (Fig. 6) must be configured first. From the “Sonar setup” menu, it is possible to define the track width of the scanned area, i.e. how wide an area the probe scans at a time. For example, with a track width of 50 metres, it is possible to scan an area 100 metres wide, i.e. 50 m each side of the boat. With the side scan model DE680D, the track width options are 10, 15, 25, 50, 75 and 100 metres at two different speeds, i.e. 1.5 and 3.0 knots. The track width selected during side scanning is displayed on the scale at the top of the waterfall window. The frequency of the DE680D emitter (680 kHz) is “fixed” and cannot be changed. It is also possible to specify in the “Towfish setup” window whether to send the sound pulses to both sides of the sonar or to one side only, i.e. “Left side” or “Right side”, where True = on and False = off). In addition, you can also choose the folder (“Directory”) into which the side scan data will be saved. The depth data storage folder is selected in the Depth Files Properties window and is located by clicking “Settings”, then “Depth”. The “Baud rate” function determines how fast data is transferred between the probe and the storage unit. The baud rate influences the resolution of the generated echo picture.

Fig 6. Towfish setup menu.

Side-scanning

Beginning the scan

After determining and arriving at the desired research area and when sea conditions are found to be suitable for side scanning, the system must first be put into operation as described above. Then using a rope and a Prusik knot to fix it in place, the towing cable is connected to the towing point of the vessel (Fig. 7), which may be at the side or rear of the craft. Once the vessel is travelling in the desired direction and has reached the correct towing speed, i.e. 1.5 or 3 knots depending on the setup, the probe can be lowered with the skipper's permission to the preferred depth and side scanning proper can begin. The so-called "10% rule" can be used to determine the optimum running depth of the fish by setting the probe so that its distance from the bottom is 10% of the track width used. For example, if the track width is 50 metres, then the optimum depth for the fish is five metres above the bottom. However, it may be necessary to make some modifications to this rule over very shallow or topographically uneven bottoms.

Fig. 7. Side scan setup in one of the Metsähallitus boats.

In some boats, the use of drogue or sea anchor is recommended (Fig. 8), which allows the boat engine to be operated at slightly higher motor speeds (rpm). The problem with some Metsähallitus boats is that at low cruising speeds, the boat's engine remains too cold and fuel mixes with the engine oil. This results in the oil being diluted and its level rising within the engine, requiring a mandatory oil change. The use of a sea anchor slows down this process. The size of the drogue depends on the size of the towing vessel used. During the summer of 2014, drogues measuring approximately 135 x 142 cm were used and worked well for boats measuring eight to nine metres in length.

Fig. 8. Drogue or sea-anchor in use.

Recording side scan sonar material

Recording the sonar material is started by pressing the sonar and depth record buttons, whereby the program begins to collect data as new side scan and depth files. Ongoing recordings appear in the "Project Navigator" window on the left side of the screen, which also shows all other side scan and depth files recorded for that project. Individual side scan and depth files from a specific area can be saved as a project, whereby all material recorded from that area can be found from one file path, which facilitates further processing of the material. To stop recording, for example, when making turns, the record buttons are pressed once again, and the recorded files are saved to their selected folders. In Summer 2014, although the depth data was recorded for the entire track length, the side scan recordings were stopped at each turn because such course changes always caused disturbance to the side scan data.

During scanning, the programme's waterfall window (upper panel) displays the real-time data collected by the side scan sonar, while the map window shows the real-time track area (in red) that the probe is covering. After scanning, the area covered by the probe turns green (Fig. 9) in the map window or if the mosaic function is selected, a sonogram is drawn in the map window. The mosaic function is selected by right-clicking the mouse in the waterfall window. From the pop-up menu, select the "Properties" function, which has the "Draw mosaic" function (True = on, False = off). During computation, the depth data collected by the programme can also be displayed in the map window by changing the depth data transparency setting found in the "Depth Files Properties" window.

Fig. 9. Side scan sonar tracks visible in the map window of the side scan programme. Tracks which have been scanned are shown in green, while the track currently being scanned is coloured red. Note the deliberate overlap between tracks to fully cover the scanning area.

Boat control during side scanning

It is always advisable to carry out side scanning with either a head- or a tailwind, since side waves cause the boat to roll, creating a lot of disturbance to the sonogram. While scanning, the ship's pilot keeps the speed and the course as steady as possible so that no disturbances caused by course changes or speed variations can be seen in the sonogram, and that parallel tracks partially overlap, so that there are no unscanned gaps in the area under investigation. If the boat has an autopilot installed, it can be used to help keep the course true.

Activities of the crew during side scanning

During scanning, the boat crew watch for stones or other obstacles to ensure the free passage of both the vessel and the probe in the water. They also control the functions of the scanning system, such as starting and stopping the recording of sonar material, e.g. when the boat is turning. In addition, they determine the layback, i.e. the horizontal distance from the probe to the towing point, which is required to determine the position information of the side scan data.

Stopping scanning and saving material

Once the scan has been completed, lift the sea-anchor and the probe into the vessel and flush the probe with fresh water. After rinsing, it is advisable to leave the probe for a moment to dry before packing it into its box. Ensure that the connection between the towing cable and the probe is dry before it is removed from the probe so that there is no risk of water entering the connector and

through it to the probe itself. Save the side scan material to the desired folder on the laptop and pack away the side scan system in its transport case.

Processing and interpreting side scan material in the DeepView 4.1 programme

Importing side scan and depth data to the side scan programme

Processing and interpretation the recorded side scan and depth data begins by importing the desired material into the side scan programme. The “Open” function in the “File” menu allows you to open a project whose material you want to process. The “Project Navigator” window on the left opens all the individual sonar and depth files that the project contains. It is also possible to import individual side scan and depth files into the programme using the “Add file” function in the “File” menu.

The sonogram

The sonogram or acoustic image of the data collected by the side scan sonar (Fig. 10) consists of so-called reflection values of the sound pulses transmitted by the side scan emitter. The magnitude of these values depends on the intensity of the returning echo. In other words, the stronger the echo, the greater the reflection value it will receive. In the sonogram, different values are displayed by their own shades, with light shades depicting high reflection values and *vice versa*. In the middle of the sonogram and directly below the probe is the nadir, which is ignored when collecting side scan material because the perpendicular reflection from the seafloor to the underside of the probe is too strong compared to the reflection from other parts of the probing area.

Fig. 10. Sonogram showing bottom features such as stones and rocks, as well as the nadir.

Processing the sonogram in the DeepView 4.1 side scan programme

The desired project or side scan files are imported into side scan programme by clicking on the side scan file displayed in the "Project Navigator" window. The sonogram contained in that file can be displayed in the waterfall window, where individual sonograms can be processed and viewed in different ways.

By right-clicking a single side scan file in the "Project Navigator" window, it is possible to open a menu that allows you to carry out several functions:

- Centre the sonogram in the map window by clicking "Centre in map"
- Export function. Save as an .xtf file
- Remove function, this function removes the side scan file from an open project but does not remove the original file.
- Properties function. Clicking this option opens a "Side scan file properties" window, which can be used to activate different filters, i.e. "Noise Filter" and "Position Filter" (False = off, True = on). These filters can be used to remove some of the disturbances contained within the sonogram. Within the "Side scan file properties" window, you can also activate the "Ground range" function (False = off, True = on) that removes the nadir from the sonogram. In addition, this menu is the location in the side scan programme where the layback is recorded, i.e. the horizontal distance from the probe to the ship's towing point (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. Schematic showing how to measure the layback distance. For more information on calculating layback, see [here](#).

The offset is also recorded here, i.e. the position of the towing point relative to the vessel's GPS antenna. The offset can be measured during scanning at sea or at a different time if the towing point on board remains constant. Using the GPS antenna as a viewpoint, the distance in metres is

recorded, i.e. D_x (m), to the right or left of the on-board towing point. When looking from the GPS, if the towing point is located to the left, D_x (m) will be recorded as a negative number. If the towing point is located to the right of the GPS antenna, the corresponding distance will be positive. Again, using the GPS antenna as a viewpoint, the distance in metres to the towing point towards the bow or the stern of the boat is recorded as D_y (m). If the towing point is located from the GPS antenna towards the rear of the vessel, that distance is recorded as a negative number. If the towing point is located from the GPS antenna towards the bow of the vessel, that distance should be recorded as a positive number (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12. Schematic showing how to measure the offset distances.

Clicking the right mouse button on the sonogram window will open a menu that will allow you to edit the sonogram in different ways.

- The 'Set bottom' function can be used to manually determine from the sonogram where the limits of the water column and bottom are located. This function may be required if the seabed topography is very variable and the programme itself cannot automatically define the boundary between the water column and the bottom in the sonogram.
- With the "Split file" function, the sonogram shown in the waterfall window can be divided into two. This function may be useful, for example, if a part of the sonogram in the waterfall window is to be cut out. When using the "Split file" function, the programme creates two new side scan files, while retaining the original, uncut file.
- The "Manual Mapping" function allows you to change the black and white balance of the sonogram. To use the "Manual Mapping" function, "Auto colour mapping" must be first deactivated in the "Side Scan Files Properties" window that opens from the "Properties" function of that menu.

- In the “Properties” window, you can also change the colour of the sonogram and determine how the “Signal strength” window at the top of the waterfall window appears (for information on the mosaic functions in the “Properties” window, see “Creating a mosaic”).

Interpreting the sonogram and producing images for publishing

Once a sonogram has been treated, it can be interpreted. Successful interpretation requires that the person making the interpretation is aware of how these images are generated, how the seabed structure, as well as the factors causing the disruption and distortion affect this process. As mentioned earlier, the sonogram produced by side scan sonar results from the intensity values of the sound pulses sent back by the reflected echo. The stronger the reflective echo, the higher the reflection value it will get. In the sonogram, different values are displayed with their own shades, with light shades depicting high reflection values and darker tones depicting low reflection values.

The most important factors influencing sonogram formation are associated with the seabed structure, such as the bottom gradient, texture, and the quality of the substrate (Fig. 10). During side scanning, the sound pulses transmitted perpendicularly to the seabed reflect a much larger number of echoes back to the probe than a surface that is inclined relative to the transmitted pulses. The seafloor facing away from the probe is generally completely invisible to the side scan pulse. In the sonogram itself, the effect of the bottom slope shows that the bottom facing towards the probe is much lighter than the one facing away from it, which usually appears in the sonogram as an almost completely black area. The same principle is based on the ability of different textures to reflect the sound pulses emitted by side scan sonar. A stony bottom offers surfaces facing in many different directions, some of which are towards the probe and some away from it. In the sonogram, such a bottom appears rough, with a variety of low and high reflection values appearing as light and dark tones, respectively. Conversely, on flat bottoms comprising bedrock, sand or silt, all surfaces usually point in the same direction, and thus this bottom type appears smooth and almost monotone in the sonogram. In practice, the quality of the bottom material affects the strength of the incoming echo and the sonogram’s appearance. Thus, the harder the bottom material is, the stronger the reflective echoes and *vice versa* for soft bottoms. Therefore, hard bottoms reflect most of the sound waves back to the probe while the soft bottom absorbs most of the pulses instead. For this reason, sonograms of bottoms composed of rock and stone are much lighter in shade than those of silt or mud seafloors.

Fig. 13. Schematic of a side scan in operation. Sound pulses reflect from surfaces (orange) but produce blind-spots behind objects or on surfaces facing away from the probe (black). Taken from DeepVision manual 3.1 “Side scan introduction”.

However, not all dark areas are soft sediments or surfaces facing away from the probe. Due to its mode of operation, the side scan sonar creates shadows in the sonogram behind objects rising from the seabed (Fig. 13). These shadows are formed when the path of the downwardly-angled sound waves leaving the emitter is prevented on encountering an object rising from the bottom, such as a large rock or boulder. The sound wave is reflected from the obstacle and the area behind it remains unscanned. The shadows in question are thus blind-spots from which no data is collected. However, despite this lack of material, these blind-spots along with their acoustic shadows are valuable for interpreting the sonogram, as the shadow corresponds to the shape of the object. When the length or area of such a shadow is known, as well as the distance of the probe from the seabed and the distance of the shadow producing object from the sonogram nadir, the height of the object producing the shadow can be calculated.

Measuring Distances

The distance measuring tool is in the side scan toolbar. This tool enables the user to measure distances in a side scan file. It can also be used to measure the length of an object that is displayed in the object view window. The measuring tool is used by first selecting the ruler icon in the side scan toolbar. Press and hold the left mouse button at the edge of the object to be measured. Hold the left mouse button as you drag the mouse to other side. The length and compass direction of the measurement are displayed in a black box in the object view. The angle displayed in the black box informs the orientation of the measured object in the map. Zero degrees corresponds to north in the map. The angle increases clockwise, which means north is zero degrees, south will be at 180 degrees, etc.

Measuring object heights

The measure height tool is located to the right of the measure distance tool and allows the user to measure the height of an object in a side scan sonar file. To measure height, select the measure height tool in the side scan toolbar. Select the bottom line where the object is by left clicking at the side of the water column. Select the start of the object's shadow by pressing the left mouse button. Left click again at the end of the shadow. A black box with information about the height appears in the object view window (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14: Height measurement of an object in the object view. The bottom line (1) is the first echo after the water column. The shadow start (2) is the part of the shadow closest to the water column. The shadow end is the part of the shadow furthest away from the water column. Taken from DeepVision side scan manual 3.2 "Measuring distance and height in side scan sonar files".

Sounds in the environment can easily cause interference, which in the sonogram appear as distortions and odd observations. Such disturbance sounds include other sonar devices, such as the towing vessel's own sonar, the towing vessel's and other boats' engine noise, echolocating aquatic animals and even the sound of rain on the water surface. During the side scan sonar investigations conducted in the summer of 2014, it was also found that even the electronics of the towing vessel, such as the ship's inverter, could cause disturbances in the sonogram. In addition, air bubbles caused by other vessels, for example, can cause errors in the scanned material, either by attenuating sound waves or by generating reflections. Fish shoals are also comparable to air bubbles, because their swim bladders effectively reflect sound waves. Thus, a fish shoal will appear clearly in the sonogram. In addition to these factors, the properties of the water column itself may cause errors in the side scanned material. Due to water stratification and other density differences, sound waves may be projected unexpectedly from the water column interfaces, creating distortions in the sonogram.

The production of high-quality side scan material requires that the probe moves evenly in the water at an optimum distance from the seabed, while the boat's speed and course are kept steady. Uncontrolled oscillation, wobbling or twisting of the probe usually results in interference and distortions in the sonogram. The reason for the poor swimming performance of the fish in the water

usually results from either an incorrect point of attachment to the probe itself or from sudden changes in the speed or course of the towing vessel. Various currents and waves can also affect the movement of the probe in the water.

In the DeepView 4.1 side scan programme, the visual interpretation of the sonograms occurs in the programme's waterfall window. Here you can view and interpret the sonogram by scrolling up and down. With the tools in the programme you can measure objects of interest in the sonogram and enlarge them also. Points of interest can also be marked for later review. Right-clicking the cursor in the waterfall window will open a menu where the "Add marker" function can mark the point of interest. The "Add marker" function works in the same way in the programme map window. All entries added to the waterfall window or the map window will appear in the "Project Navigator" window, along with the side scan and depth files. By right-clicking a single marker in the "Project Navigator" window, you can focus the marker in the map window with the "Centre in map" function or delete it with the "Remove" function. In the menu that opens by clicking the "Properties" function, you can also change the name, location or appearance of that marker. Markers added to the map window or sonogram can be saved in GPX file format, which allows them to be exported to mapping programmes, such as ArcGIS, or as video or dive points on those boat plotters that support GPX file format. However, GPX files may first have to be converted to another format using conversion programmes like GPS Utility. For example, in older Raymarine chart plotters, GPX files must first be converted to FSH format archive files before they can be displayed. Markers can be saved in GPX format in by right-clicking the "Markers" folder in the "Project Navigator" window. From the menu that opens, the "Export" function is selected, after which the file is saved in the desired folder. Markers can also be saved in Google Earth format, i.e. as .kmz files. In this menu, it is also possible to import spatial data, such as video- or dive points in GPX format by clicking the "Import" function.

When the sonogram in the waterfall window has been interpreted, it is possible to produce images for publishing by right-clicking on the waterfall window and selecting the "Report" option from the menu that opens. In the "Scan report settings" window, the image size, background colour, and other desired settings can be defined, after which the image can be saved to the desired folder, either by selecting the .png or .jpeg file options. In addition to these images, individual sonograms can also be saved as XTF files. This is done by right-clicking on the individual side scan file in the "Project Navigator" window. From the menu that opens, the "Export" function is selected, after which the file is saved in the desired folder.

Creating, processing and exporting a mosaic

The first step when creating a mosaic is to check in the map window if the area scanned looks like a cluster of mini sonograms or a colourful mosaic (Fig. 15). If it is the former, right click on the Depth Log Files folder in the Project Navigator window. Click on the Properties function to open the Depth Files Properties menu. Change "Transparency" from "True" to "False" and click OK to make the colourful mosaic visible in the Map window. The appearance of this colourful mosaic can be changed

by changing the options in the Depth Log Files Properties menu. The functions of this menu are as follows:

Fig. 15. Screenshot of DeepView 4.1 with colour mosaic of the scanned area in the lower map window.

Depth Map Creation:

- **Outer Radius (m):** this feature allows the scan width of each track to be changed. If the original scan width is 100 metres, the scan width shown in the depth mosaic can be narrowed or widened. However, some caution should be used. Too narrow track widths may not fully use the scanned data from the field and some features will be lost, while too wide track widths lead to over-extrapolation and the possible creation of artefacts on the seabed.
- **Details:** the level of detail within the depth mosaic is on a scale from 1.0 to 10.0, with the former showing a smoothed surface, while the latter has a much greater level of detail. This feature is important as there may be restrictions on publishing detailed side scan map information when reporting.

Depth Scale:

- **Auto Min/Max Depth:** This feature allows the user to manually select the minimum and maximum depths of the depth profile by changing the option from “True” to “False”, then changing the minimum and maximum depth scale boxes to the desired depths. This feature can be used to examine a specific depth scale of interest.

Colours:

- “Colours” allows the user to select a variety of colour scales to display the depth mosaic by clicking an option on the drop-down menu. The option “Depth 1” is often selected as it shows depths on a rainbow spectrum with deeper areas as blue and purple and shallowest areas as orange and red.
- The option “Reverse Colours”, inverts this colour-depth relationship by selecting “False”.
- The option “Discrete Colours” creates a border line between colours if “True” is selected. If “False” is selected, the colours blend into one another.
- There is a number scale of 1 to 30 colours for the option “Discrete Steps”. Here, 1 will produce only a single colour, whereas 30 will give the full colour spectrum for the depth data and therefore, more detail of the bottom topography.
- “Transparency” and “Transparency Level” relate to whether the colour mosaic is visible or not, or if the user wishes to view both the colour mosaic as well as the sonogram tracks in the map window, its transparency can be changed accordingly on a scale of 1 to 10. 1 is almost completely transparent and only the sonogram mosaic is visible, 10 is completely opaque with only the colour mosaic visible.

Transducer:

- The options for this function are described below in the Depth File Properties section.

To create a three-dimensional profile of a scanned area, click the “Select Area” icon in the toolbar and select the area you wish to use within the map window. Then right-click on this area to open a menu. A marker can be added to the colour mosaic by clicking “Add Marker” and processing such markers is like that described above for interpreting the sonogram. Clicking “Report” opens a menu entitled “Selected Area Report Settings” which allows options for changing the appearance of a two-dimensional colour mosaic. The files produced can be in several formats, i.e. png, jpeg, geoTIFF, or kmz. The latter files will open in mapping programmes, such as ArcGIS and Google Earth. To produce a three-dimensional image, click “3D” and an image will open in the upper pane. The image has a red arrow which points North, a white arrow pointing South and can be rotated in all directions. The three-dimensional image can be saved by right-clicking the image and selecting “Report”. The image is saved in either png format or as a jpeg image. In addition, its appearance can be modified by clicking on “Properties” (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16. Screenshot of DeepView 4.1 with colour mosaic of the scanned area in the lower map window and a three-dimensional representation in the upper pane.

Depth material

Depth information processing and interpretation

Once the desired project or depth files have been imported into the side scan programme by clicking on the individual depth files displayed “Project Navigator” window, the depth profile contained in that file can be displayed in the programme's waterfall window. The depth data itself is drawn in the programme's map window, where different depths are marked with different colour tones.

Right-clicking within the “Project Navigator” window on a single depth file opens a menu that allows you to focus on the depth data contained in that file in the map window by clicking the “Centre in map” function. The depth data can be exported in .csv format using the Export function. In addition, the depth file can be removed from the project using the “Remove” function. As described above, although the “Remove” function removes the depth file from an open project, it does not delete the original file. Selecting the “Properties” function opens a “Depth Log Properties” window.

Depth files properties

- Model: This is the model or type of the vessel's echosounder or transducer
- Lobe width: This is the angle of sonar beam in degrees produced by the transducer.
- Frequency: This is the frequency of the sonar pulse in kilohertz.

- DX (m) and DY (m) are the transducer position relative to the GPS antenna. DX (m) is measured from the transducer to the right or left of the GPS antenna. To the right of the antenna gives a positive value and to the left a negative value. If the transducer is located forward of the GPS antenna, i.e. towards the bow, the position value is positive. If the transducer is positioned behind the GPS antenna, i.e. towards the stern, its value is negative (Fig. 17).
- Depth (m) refers to the depth of the transducer underwater relative to the surface. A positive value means it is located beneath the surface.

Fig. 17. Schematic for measuring depth log properties D_x (m) and D_y (m) based on the position of the transducer relative to the GPS antenna.

Appendix II: Field protocols

Video protocol:

Site:			Date:					
Persons:			Camera:					
Boat:			DEPTH		GPS #			
Video ID	Time	Point name	Start	End	Start	End	Secchi	Notes
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								
11								
12								
13								
14								
15								
16								
17								
18								
19								
20								
21								
22								
23								
24								
25								
26								
27								
28								
29								
30								
31								
32								
33								
34								
35								
36								
37								
38								
39								
40								

Dive plan protocol:
Dive record

Dive officer

Dive location										Date	
Mission											
Before dive								After dive			
Diver	Assistant	Tank volume litres/bar	Start pressure	Weight belt/kg	Planned depth/time	Descent time	Deadline	On surface	Bottom time	Max depth	Final pressure
1.											
2.											
1.											
2.											
Extra info & observations											

Dive record

Dive officer

Dive location										Date	
Mission											
Before dive								After dive			
Diver	Assistant	Tank volume litres/bar	Start pressure	Weight belt/kg	Planned depth/time	Descent time	Deadline	On surface	Bottom time	Max depth	Final pressure
1.											
2.											
1.											
2.											
Extra info & observations											

Dive record

Dive officer

Dive location										Date	
Mission											
Before dive								After dive			
Diver	Assistant	Tank volume litres/bar	Start pressure	Weight belt/kg	Planned depth/time	Descent time	Deadline	On surface	Bottom time	Max depth	Final pressure
1.											
2.											
1.											
2.											
Extra info & observations											

Dive record

Dive officer

Dive location										Date	
Mission											
Before dive								After dive			
Diver	Assistant	Tank volume litres/bar	Start pressure	Weight belt/kg	Planned depth/time	Descent time	Deadline	On surface	Bottom time	Max depth	Final pressure
1.											
2.											
1.											
2.											
Extra info & observations											

Field log protocol:

Field log

Date

Weather

Air °C	Water °C	Wind	Wind hindrance
Cloud cover	Sea level <i>cm</i>	Rain	Rain hindrance
Secchi <i>m</i>	Algal bloom 0-3	(Degree: 0 = no probs 1 = some 2 = much 3 = stops work)	

Boat + Crew

Area

Video filming/Raking

Filmed points (No.)

SCUBA diving

Dive lines (no.)

Kautskys (no.)

(sample jar labels)

Successful photos (no.)

GPS-device name

Course of the day and events

Depart time:

Return time:

Dive log protocol:

DIVE 1

Boat + crew	Area (square)	
Location		
Coords N	Coords E	Boat/shore?
Dive mission		
Diver	Surface-assistant	
Line length (m	Distance of line start from the waterline (m)	
Line direction in degrees (from line start)		

DIVE 2

Boat + crew	Area (square)	
Location		
Coords N	Coords E	Boat/shore?
Dive mission		
Diver	Surface-assistant	
Line length (m	Distance of line start from the waterline (m)	
Line direction in degrees (from line start)		

DIVE 3

Boat + crew	Area (square)	
Location		
Coords N	Coords E	Boat/shore?
Dive mission		
Diver	Surface-assistant	
Line length (m	Distance of line start from the waterline (m)	
Line direction in degrees (from line start)		

DIVE 4

Boat + crew	Area (square)	
Location		
Coords N	Coords E	Boat/shore?
Dive mission		
Diver	Surface-assistant	
Line length (m	Distance of line start from the waterline (m)	
Line direction in degrees (from line start)		

DIVE 5

Boat + crew	Area (square)	
Location		
Coords N	Coords E	Boat/shore?
Dive mission		
Diver	Surface-assistant	
Line length (m	Distance of line start from the waterline (m)	
Line direction in degrees (from line start)		

Appendix III: LajiGIS Marine methodology codes

LajiGIS-marine methodology codes	
Mapping method (mandatory):	Mapping method clarification
13 = Trap	10 = Video, low resolution
20 = Mapping at sea, unspecified	11 = Video, HD resolution
21 = Line dive	13 = Snorkelling
22 = Raking	14 = Rake + rope
23 = Aquascope	15 = Poled rake
24 = Photography	16 = Kick- or poled net
25 = Spot diving	17 = van Veen grab
26 = Benthic sampling	18 = Box-corer
27 = Dive sampling	19 = Ekman grab
28 = General observations while diving	20 = Ponar grab
33 = Helicopter	21 = Tvärminne-sampler
34 = Helicopter, remote-controlled	22 = Core sampler
41 = Acoustic sounding	23 = Collection sample, qualitative
42 = Drop-video filming	24 = Kautsky square
43 = ROV	25 = Suction sampler
44 = Video + rake	26 = Fucus-bag sampler
45 = Mapping by aircraft	27 = Side scan sonar
	28 = SCUBA diving
	29 = Helicopter or aeroplane
	30 = Other autonomous devices
	31 = Net fishing
	32 = Hand netting
	33 = Fish trap or similar

Appendix IV: Rubbish categories and codes

Rubbish categories		
Material:	Code	Waste type:
Plastic	PL01	Bottle corks and caps
Plastic	PL02	Bottles > 2 L
Plastic	PL03	Bottles, barrels, jerrycans & buckets > 2 L
Plastic	PL04	Knives, forks, spoons, straws, spatulas (cutlery)
Plastic	PL05	Six-pack rings, drink package rings
Plastic	PL06	Food containers (fast food, glasses, lunch boxes & similar)
Plastic	PL07	plastic bags (matt & clear)
Plastic	PL08	Toys & party poppers
Plastic	PL09	Gloves
Plastic	PL10	Cigarette lighters
Plastic	PL11	Cigarettes, butts and filters
Plastic	PL12	Syringes
Plastic	PL13	Crates, drink crates and trays
Plastic	PL14	Plastic floats
Plastic	PL15	Nets bags (vegetable, oyster- & mussel bags)
Plastic	PL16	Tarpaulins or other woven plastic bags, stretch wrap
Plastic	PL17	Angling gear (lures, traps & crab pots)
Plastic	PL18	Monofilament fishing line
Plastic	PL19	Ropes
Plastic	PL20	Fishing nets
Plastic	PL21	Strapping
Plastic	PL22	Fibreglass pieces
Plastic	PL23	Resin pellets
Plastic	PL24	Other (specify)
Foam plastic	FP01	Sponges
Foam plastic	FP02	Mugs & food packaging
Foam plastic	FP03	Foam plastic floats
Foam plastic	FP04	Foam (insulation & packaging)
Foam plastic	FP05	Other (specify)
Fabric	CL01	Clothing, shoes, hats & towels
Fabric	CL02	Rucksacks & cases
Fabric	CL03	Oilcloth, sail canvas & sackcloth (hessian)
Fabric	CL04	Ropes and strings
Fabric	CL05	Mats and furniture
Fabric	CL06	Other fabrics containing rags
Glass & ceramics	GC01	Construction materials (brick, cement, ducting)
Glass & ceramics	GC02	Bottles & jars
Glass & ceramics	GC03	China (plates & cups)
Glass & ceramics	GC04	Lightbulbs
Glass & ceramics	GC05	Fluorescent tubes
Glass & ceramics	GC06	Glass floats
Glass & ceramics	GC07	Glass or ceramic shards
Glass & ceramics	GC08	Other (specify)
Metal	ME01	Plates, cups & cutlery
Metal	ME02	Bottles corks, lids and ringpulls
Metal	ME03	Aluminium cans
Metal	ME04	Other cannisters (< 4 L)
Metal	ME05	Gas bottles, barrels & buckets (> 4 L)
Metal	ME06	Foil wrap
Metal	ME07	Fishing-related (weights, lures, hooks, traps & crab pots)
Metal	ME08	Pieces
Metal	ME09	Wire cables, wire mesh & barbed wire
Metal	ME10	Other (specify), including electronic devices

Rubbish categories		
Material:	Code	Waste type:
Paper & carton	PC01	Paper (including newspapers & magazines)
Paper & carton	PC02	Cardboard boxes & pieces
Paper & carton	PC03	Cups, utensils, food wrapping, cigarette cartons, drink containers
Paper & carton	PC04	Firework tubes
Paper & carton	PC05	Other (specify)
Rubber	RB01	Balloons, balls and toys
Rubber	RB02	Shoes (sandals)
Rubber	RB03	Gloves
Rubber	RB04	Tyres
Rubber	RB05	Inner tubes and rubber sheets
Rubber	RB06	Rubber bands
Rubber	RB07	Condoms
Rubber	RB08	Other (specify)
Wood	WD01	Corks
Wood	WD02	Fishing traps and crab pots
Wood	WD03	Ice pop sticks, forks, chopsticks and toothpicks
Wood	WD04	Processed wood and pallet boxes
Wood	WD05	Matches & fireworks
Wood	WD06	Other (specify)
Other	OT01	Parafin or wax
Other	OT02	Sanitary products (nappies, ear buds, tampon applicators, toothbrushes)
Other	OT03	Electrical devices & electronics
Other	OT04	Batteries (household)
Other	OT05	Other (specify)
Organic	OR02	Manure
Organic	OR03	Fruit, food, pastry, candy, ice-cream
Organic	OR04	Other organic material (specify)